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InBestSoil

Monetary valuation of soil ecosystem services and creation of initiatives to invest in soil health: setting a framework for the inclusion of soil health in business and in the policy making process- InBestSoil

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D4.1. – Systematic overview (map) of current archetypes, drivers and barriers for sustainable business models related to soil health

Systematic overview (map) of current archetypes, drivers and barriers for sustainable business models related to soil health

Summary

This document outlines a soil-health-based Sustainable Business Model (SBM) approach tailored to the European context, adapting traditional SBM dimensions to emphasize ecosystem services, specific land-use practices, and partnerships for delivering value to stakeholders, including society and the environment.

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1. Introduction

This deliverable aims to present the current state-of-the-art literature on business models, archetypes, and approaches related to soil health within the European context. It analyses potential business models for sustainability and synthesizes available approaches into an *Integrated Soil-health-based Sustainable Business Model (SBM) Approach*. This SBM approach serves as a comprehensive map containing practical guides, examples, and available options for various professionals in Europe, including farmers, LLs and LHs coordinators, agronomists, agri-tech providers, agricultural consultants, environmental organizations, and policymakers. Its practical purpose is to assist these stakeholders in exploring, improving, and integrating soil health practices into business models, even if they are unsure of where to begin. By consolidating advanced knowledge on soil health-related business models and sustainable agricultural practices, this document aims to enable informed decision-making. Additionally, it helps practitioners align with regulatory trends, manage environmental risks, and effectively engage with policymakers and citizens.

A business model is a tool that links a firm's strategy to its activities, helping it think strategically about its operations. A business model can be viewed from the perspective of value. First, there is the Value Proposition, which refers to the value that a business aims to provide to customers who are interested in that value. Next, there is value creation and delivery, which involves organizing activities and resources in order to create and deliver that value. Lastly, there is value capture, which pertains to how a business benefits from delivering such value to their customers or end users (Richardson, 2008). These elements together reflect the strategic logic of value in a business model.

SBMs adapt conventional business models by incorporating *sustainability* dimensions into their value components. They are characterized by proactive multi-stakeholder management, the creation of both monetary and non-monetary value for a wide range of stakeholders, and a long-term perspective (Geissdoerfer et al., 2018).

Traditionally, SBMs have been developed mainly for firms and business executives, focusing on the economic, social, and environmental dimensions within corporate contexts (Bocken et al., 2014; Elkington & Rowlands, 1999). However, farms and businesses directly or indirectly connected to soil have unique contexts and concerns such as soil health, fertility management, erosion control, and/or the impact of agricultural practices on ecosystem services. Traditional SBMs often fail to address the specific attributes of soil-related enterprises, including farms. Consequently, stakeholders in these sectors may encounter difficulties in relating to and effectively applying standard business models. This can potentially impede their efforts to achieve sustainability and operational efficiency. Thus, this deliverable addresses the gap by providing an integrated soil-health-based SBM approach (tailored to the European context).

This approach builds on the original SBM archetypes identified by Bocken et al. (2014) for industry sustainability and the extended version by Ritala et al. (2018). The theoretical facets of these original archetypes served as a foundation for identifying archetypes in this work. However, as expected, despite conceptual overlaps, some of the dimensions, archetypes and sub-archetypes needed to be modified and some were replaced by new ones¹, with value components specific to the context of soil health (and sustainable agriculture). Hence, in the context of soil health, the value proposition encompasses various ecosystem services provided by soil. Value creation and delivery involve the implementation of specific land-use and soil-health practices and innovations, in addition to the formation of partnerships required to generate these ecosystem services and deliver the created value to stakeholders, including the environment and society. Finally, value capture refers to reduced costs, improved crop yields, and enhanced resilience to climate change, as well as the mechanisms through which land users, as stewards of the soil, obtain value from the ecosystem services facilitated by adopting certain land-use practices over others.

As a methodology, a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) was conducted to identify the SBM archetypes and their value components. An SLR is a structured approach used to analyse and synthesize the existing research on soil and business-related studies within Europe. The Scopus database was chosen for its broad coverage across various research disciplines. The search query used the keyword "soil health" in combination with terms related to business and sustainability. This search, limited to journal articles and reviews in English, yielded 2,769 documents. To refine the scope to the European context, the query was further limited to include all European countries and their derivatives, eventually resulting in 215 studies. The collected articles were reviewed, codified, and classified into identified dimensions and archetypes. Each dimension consists of related archetypes and sub-archetypes, which are presented in Section 2 as an integrated soil-health-based SBM approach. To further explore the factors influencing the adoption or non-adoption of soil health-related practices, interviews were conducted with arable farmers in the Netherlands.

As shown in Table 1, the Soil-health-based SBM approach consists of three dimensions and nine archetypes linked to these dimensions. The dimensions are "Environmental-Technological", "Social-Organizational", and "Economic". The first two are entirely new, while the latter one has been established in the previous literature. The Environmental-Technological dimension covers four archetypes including optimizing resource use efficiency, reducing emissions and pollution, fostering natural cycles, and substituting with the best conservation practices. The archetypes included in the Social-Organizational dimension are about scanning and integrating of soil science, facilitating sustainability transitions, and

¹ For example, the dimensions of "Environmental-Technological" and "Social-Organizational" or the archetype "Scan, Learn, and Integrate Soil Science" appear as entirely new in the soil health context, while the "Develop Diversified and Productive Solutions" archetype follows the logic of the economic archetype developed in the original framework, i.e., "Develop Scale-up Solutions."

encouraging sufficiency while considering cultural values. Finally, the Economic dimension involves two archetypes including creating inclusive value through innovative approaches and developing diversified and productive solutions. The (sub-)archetypes of one dimension may overlap with those of another dimension. However, the authors maintain consistency by forming the archetypes and sub-archetypes based on value logic behind these strategies and solutions.

Table 1. An Integrated Soil-health-based SBM approach with new and modified archetypes

Dimension	Environmental- Technological	Social- Organizational	Economic
Archetypes specific to soil-health-based SBM	1. Optimize Use Efficiency (modified) 2. Reduce/Remediate Emissions and Pollution (modified) 3. Foster Natural Cycles (modified) 4. Substitute with Conservation (Best Management) Practices (modified)	5. Scan, Learn, and Integrate Soil Science (new) 6. Facilitate Sustainability Transitions (new) 7. Encourage Sufficiency and Consider Cultural Values (modified)	8. Create Inclusive Value through Innovative Approaches (modified) 9. Develop Diversified and Productive Solutions (modified)

Note: The revised archetypes (newly created or modified), compared to the archetypes from Bocken et al. (2014) and Ritala et al. (2018), are specified in parentheses in front of each one.

Additionally, the report highlights the drivers and barriers to adopting soil health practices, particularly categorized within the archetype 6 “Facilitate Sustainability Transitions.” This archetype was chosen because the literature indicates that driving soil health adoption and reinforcing sustainable agriculture requires interdisciplinary, systematic, and collaborative facilitation efforts to overcome challenges at various levels. The findings from the SLR were complemented by an empirical investigation of the drivers and barriers in the Dutch context.

The results underline four major adoption factors: Knowledge/Social Networks, Institutional, Technical, and Personal. Key insights from these interviews are summarized in Annex 2. This empirical evidence aligns with the findings from the SLR, providing a more comprehensive view of the challenges and opportunities in promoting soil health within the European agricultural context.

The newly discovered and modified dimensions and archetypes from the integrated Soil-health-based SBM Approach provide a map that guides stakeholders with explanations and examples towards available options for soil

health sustainability. Based on the key findings of each study and their implications for practice and research, the integrated soil-health-based SBM approach provides empirical examples of soil health practices and recommendations for their adoption for each archetype and sub-archetype. These examples and recommendations are also listed in Annex 1, along with additional details. It assists the stakeholders in; 1) understanding soil health-related business models and sustainable agricultural practices 2) exploring and integrating soil health practices into business models, 3) making informed decisions and 4) aligning with regulatory trends to manage environmental risks. It specifically empowers the agricultural sector to adopt innovative, sustainable practices, fostering resilience, competitiveness, and meaningful contributions to environmental sustainability and policy development².

While most recommendations are broadly applicable, some are highly context-specific, depending on particular European geographical and climatic conditions, soil characteristics, and other pertinent factors.

2. Soil-Health-Based SBM Framework (archetypes, drivers, and barriers)

In Section 2, the archetypes, sub-archetypes, and underlying themes are presented in detail. Each archetype begins with a box containing a brief description, including its focus and strategies for value creation, delivery, and

² The focus on agriculture came out of the dataset and was not a preconceived restriction on the review.

capture. This box also highlights the intended audience who play a key role and can benefit from the archetype based on its relevance.

2.1. Environmental-Technological Dimension

This SBM dimension focuses on implementing soil-health-based practices and innovations to address environmental issues and create sustainable values. The four archetypes identified and discussed within this dimension are “Optimize Use Efficiency,” “Reduce/Remediate Emissions and Pollution,” “Foster Natural Cycles,” and “Substitute with Conservation (Best Management) Practices.” Each archetype begins with a concise summary that introduces the value components and key stakeholders, tailored to the specific context of soil health and its environmental challenges.

2.1.1. Archetype 1- Optimize Use Efficiency

This soil-health-based SBM archetype emphasizes sustainable soil health management while addressing climate change impacts, optimizing water and nutrient use, and ensuring land productivity. Strategies such as precision agriculture, efficient irrigation, and tailored fertilization enhance resource use efficiency. By applying this approach, agriculturists benefit from soil health, reduced input costs, and crop productivity, and contribute to the conservation of natural resources and improvement of environmental sustainability.

- ✚ **Value proposition:** Enhancing soil health and agricultural productivity by ensuring that more resources (i.e., water, nutrients, and land) are left for nature or other societal purposes.
- ✚ **Value Creation & Delivery:** Implementing precision agriculture techniques, efficient irrigation systems, and tailored fertilization practices. These strategies optimize resource use, reduce waste, and improve overall land productivity while contributing to environmental sustainability.
- ✚ **Value Capture:** Reduced input costs, increased crop yields, and improved environmental sustainability. The latter’s value can be captured through different pathways such as certification schemes, environmental subsidies, or other market-based rewarding mechanisms.
- ✚ **Key Targeted Stakeholders:** Farmers/agriculturists, agri-tech providers, agri-food companies, and agricultural consultants.

2.1.1.1. Water-Use Efficiency and Irrigation Practices

Efficient water management is crucial for mitigating the adverse effects of climate change on agriculture and water resources.

- In water scarce regions: Transitioning from traditional flood irrigation to drip irrigation (DI) significantly improves water use efficiency. However, DI may deplete soil nutrients away from emitters, necessitating careful evaluation to protect soil health and minimize environmental impacts (Puy et al., 2017). Hence, analyzing irrigation water quality using multivariate techniques helps identify key parameters and understand spatio-temporal variations, informing sustainable irrigation management and enhancing crop productivity (Yurtseven et al., 2020).
- Considering the use of treated wastewater for irrigation can be beneficial, serving as a viable alternative water resource in water-scarce regions. However, it may reduce yield compared to freshwater, necessitating balanced and integrated water resource management (Kayikcioglu, 2018). In addition, assessing the impact of irrigation practices on Mediterranean agricultural soils reveals that drip and sprinkler systems reduce soil organic matter and increase soil salinity compared to rainfed systems. Therefore, adopting management strategies to mitigate these effects (Telo da Gama et al., 2023) and considering specific irrigation systems and associated soil practices are needed for maintaining soil health and productivity.

2.1.1.2. Nutrient-Use Efficiency

Nutrient use efficiency is important for sustainable agriculture. Improving fertilization practices in the Mediterranean region by maintaining soil phosphorus levels (Olsen-P) below 53 mg P kg⁻¹ is recommended to prevent leaching and minimize environmental impacts. In the same vein, regular soil testing and careful use of organic amendments are crucial for the management of efficiencies (Ortiz et al., 2023). Research demonstrates that optimizing fertilizer use and managing livestock manure can contribute to nitrogen use efficiency (Misselbrook et al., 2022). Additionally, maintaining species diversity in mixed pastures by managing pasture height and avoiding excessive nitrogen rates promotes functional diversity without reducing forage production (Barreta et al., 2023). These practices help ensure nutrient use is optimized and environmental impacts are minimized.

2.1.1.3. Land-Use Decisions/Management

Prioritizing land-use management practices tailored to specific habitat types, based on soil physicochemical properties, helps maintain soil carbon levels and pH balance, thereby supporting sustainable agriculture and environmental conservation (Seaton et al., 2021). Developing high-resolution soil organic carbon (SOC) maps at the field scale by integrating environmental covariates and crop data aids in maintaining SOC levels and optimizing sustainable land-use decisions (Zhou et al., 2022). Particularly, optimizing land-use intensity in vulnerable Mediterranean systems by balancing traditional practices with modern management approaches accelerates the transition towards the sustainable provisioning of ecosystem services (Gazol et al., 2021). Eventually, to mitigate climate change impacts, it is advised to adopt climate-smart agriculture practices, develop climate-resistant crops, and use rapid evidence assessments to evaluate agricultural tools' environmental costs and benefits (Srivastav et al., 2021; Green et al., 2023).

2.1.2. Archetype 2- Reduce/Remediate Emissions and Pollution

This soil-health-based SBM archetype focuses on incorporating soil remediation strategies into the core of a business model to mitigate the environmental impact of agricultural practices and enhance soil health. By adopting innovative approaches to reduce emissions, enhance soil carbon sequestration, reduce heavy metal mobility, and remediate soil pollution, farmers support sustainable agriculture and climate change adaptation and contribute to cleaner air and water.

- ✚ **Value Proposition:** Contributing to cleaner air and water (i.e. regulating ecosystem services) by adopting practices that remediate emissions and pollution.
- ✚ **Value Creation & Delivery:** Using innovative agricultural techniques, soil carbon sequestration, and pollution mitigation strategies, this value is delivered to wider society free of charge.
- ✚ **Value Capture:** Enhanced soil health, reduced environmental impact, and compliance with environmental regulations. While the sustainability value created is a public good and challenging to capture directly, it can be monetized through Payments for Ecosystem Services (PES), subsidy schemes, and certifications that reward practices reducing emissions and pollution.
- ✚ **Key Targeted Stakeholders:** Farmers/agriculturists, agronomists, agri-tech providers, agricultural consultants, environmental organizations/NGOs, and policymakers.

2.1.2.1.Reduce Emissions

Technologically Innovative Agricultural Practices: Innovative approaches in digital agriculture, crop genetics, microbial genetics, and electrification are essential to reduce emissions in row-crop agriculture (Northrup et al., 2021). Using biopreparations like essential oils, plant extracts, marine algae extracts, and microbial agents such as *Azotobacter chroococcum* and *Azospirillum brasilense* can improve soil health and reduce CO₂ emissions, enhancing soil porosity and stabilizing emissions over time (Buragiene et al., 2023).

Soil Carbon Sequestration: Enhancing soil carbon sequestration and minimizing fertilizer use after legume cover crops can reduce emissions while improving soil water management, reducing erosion vulnerability, and retaining nitrogen under warming conditions (Kaye & Quemada, 2017). On the same note, the implementation of the “4 per 1000” initiative and negative emission technologies in collaboration with industry and the private sector accelerates soil carbon sequestration, contributing significantly to global climate change mitigation and enhancing ecosystem services (Lal, 2020). In addition, recognizing the impact of

climate change and land use on SOC turnover is fundamental. Hence, implementing mitigation measures such as crop rotation changes to counteract SOC losses and prioritizing soil management practices to enhance SOC sequestration and preserve existing stocks are pivotal for aiding climate change mitigation (Gutierrez et al., 2023).

Soil Rehabilitation and Phytostabilization: Phytostabilization with Mediterranean shrubs and liming in mine-impacted regions can enhance soil quality and support successful soil rehabilitation and revegetation efforts (Moreno-Jiménez et al., 2012).

2.1.2.2. Mitigate Soil Pollution

Addressing soil pollution through various strategies is necessary for protecting both soil health and human health. Using low-Cd phosphorus fertilizers, cultivating Cd-resistant crop varieties, promoting nutrient use efficiency, and exploring soil phytoremediation techniques are effective measures to mitigate cadmium contamination (Suciu et al., 2022). Ensuring appropriate sludge management and mitigating soil pollution with microplastics require collaboration with multiple stakeholders (Milojevic et al., 2021). Additionally, exploring additives like carbon nanotubes and clay to reduce heavy metal mobility in contaminated soils can promote soil health and sustainability (Correia et al., 2020).

Proactive strategies are key to maintaining soil health and biodiversity, particularly in urban and degraded environments. Thorough soil mapping and risk assessment in urban areas are crucial for safeguarding community health from heavy metal contamination, especially for children. This emphasizes the need for proactive pollution monitoring in urban agriculture and public health initiatives (Świdwa-Urbańska & Battle-Sales, 2021). Preserving biodiversity and soil functions in urban green spaces by addressing even low pollution levels is recommended for sustainable agriculture (Tóth et al., 2023).

2.1.3. Archetype 3- Foster Natural Cycles

This soil-health-based SBM archetype aims to leverage nature-based solutions by using organic amendments to improve soil fertility, reduce waste, and support the circular economy. Ecosystems inherently rely on various cycles that maintain dynamic equilibrium, where nutrients cycle through the system: soil feeds plants, plants feed animals, and animal waste returns to the soil. Farmers can learn from these natural processes to enhance sustainability. By adding organic materials and fostering reciprocal relationships between soil organisms and plant roots, this strategy promotes soil health, boosts plant growth, and supports essential ecosystem services.

- ✚ **Value Proposition:** Enhancing soil health, carbon sequestration and biodiversity through the lens of natural processes and organic amendments (i.e. supporting ecosystem services).
- ✚ **Value Creation & Delivery:** Applying compost, biochar, and green manure, and promoting symbiotic relationships between plants and soil organisms.
- ✚ **Value Capture:** Improved soil structure, increased biodiversity, sustainable nutrient cycles, reduced waste, reduced reliance on synthetic inputs, increased carbon sequestration, and increased crop productivity. PES schemes, subsidies, certifications, and land funds can be considered the main sources for capturing the value of the sustainability benefits created as public goods.
- ✚ **Key Targeted Stakeholders:** Farmers/agriculturists, soil amendment suppliers, agri-tech providers, agri-food companies, agricultural consultants, and environmental organizations/NGOs.

2.1.3.1. Organic Amendments (creating value from waste)

Organic Fertilization and Compost: Utilizing compost and pig slurry effectively enhances soil fertility while reducing waste, aligning with circular economy principles (Pardo et al., 2011). Compost from municipal waste sustains wheat productivity and soil fertility by increasing SOC content, though it may impact grain quality (Leogrande et al., 2016). Spent mushroom substrate serves as an effective organic manure, improving soil structure and quality; however, it is essential to analyze its nutrient content due to variability among sources (Velusami et al., 2021). Recognizing the positive impact of dung application on soil health in temperate grasslands, it is essential to prioritize its use to maintain SOC, nitrogen levels, and earthworm abundance (Segura et al., 2023). Additionally, adopting alternative management systems with organic fertilization for forage production in dairy farms improves soil health by increasing earthworm abundance and enhancing soil infiltration (Baizán et al., 2021). Combining NPK fertilizer with vermicompost and organic mulching enhances shoot growth and pod yield of beans, although care must be taken to manage potential reductions in nodulation due to decreased soil oxygenation (Singh et al., 2011).

Biochar and Bio-Based Fertilizers: Exploring the potential of rabbit manure-derived biochar, particularly at lower production temperatures, enhances soil quality and carbon sequestration in mining soils (Cárdenas-Aguilar et al., 2022). Biochar from sewage sludge, olive-mill waste, and compost sustainably enhances tomato growth in the Mediterranean region, although sawdust biochar may not yield the same benefits (Lilli et al., 2023). Further, Biochar-based smart fertilizers offer promising solutions for enhancing soil quality and crop productivity sustainably (Abiola et al., 2023). Recycled bio-based fertilizers derived from waste streams can replace conventional phosphorus fertilizers in grasslands, significantly altering soil microbial and nematode communities while maintaining microbial diversity (Karpinska et al., 2021). Bio-based fertilizers (BBF) effectively manage bio-waste and improve soil health, but addressing contamination risks and social acceptance hurdles is critical. Investing in technology development and environmental risk assessments is essential to advance BBF adoption, supporting sustainable agriculture and the circular economy (Kurniawati et al., 2023).

Green Manure and Crop Residues: Using organic amendments and green manure boosts SOC, enhances nitrogen use efficiency, and reduces nitrate leaching, providing long-term benefits for sustainable farming (Piccini et al., 2023). In the same vein, incorporating crop residues such as winter oilseed rape, faba beans, and sawdust reduces nitrogen losses, improves water quality, and cuts greenhouse gas emissions. Notably, prioritizing crop residues from the previous crop is most effective, depending on the type of amendment and field conditions (Rothardt & Kage, 2023). Maintaining SOC levels by returning crop residues and adding manures is also necessary for sustaining soil health, especially in tropical climates where SOC loss is rapid (Powlson et al., 2022). Incorporating organic amendments, particularly in woody crops, further boosts SOC storage rates in Mediterranean agricultural soils, aiding in climate change mitigation and adaptation efforts (Francaviglia et al., 2019). However, extreme winter flooding can temporarily impact soil quality and vegetation biomass production in agroecosystems. Improved management strategies are needed to expedite recovery and restore agricultural productivity after flood events (Harvey et al., 2019).

Specialized Soil Amendments: Integrating drinking-water treatment residuals (DWTR) with lime improves soil quality and reduces metal extractability in mining-affected soils, with supplemental organic or mineral fertilizers further enhancing overall soil health (Alvarenga et al., 2018). Utilizing ash from residual forest biomass combustion serves as another sustainable solution for restoring degraded mining soils by correcting soil pH, reducing metal bioavailability, and enhancing soil organism survival and reproduction (Mendes et al., 2021). Moreover, bio-stabilized material (BSM) from municipal solid wastes, combined with Brassica napus cultivation, enhances soil productivity, plant growth, and microbial activity, providing a sustainable solution for ecosystem restoration and circular economy practices (Míguez et al., 2020). Promoting the continued land application of pulp and paper mill sludge (PPMS) as a sustainable soil amendment is also significant for improving soil health in agriculture (Turner et al., 2022). On the same note, research shows that optimizing biosolids application rates balances nutrient supply and organic matter benefits with potential heavy metal accumulation, ensuring soil

microbial diversity and community structure remain optimal for long-term soil health at sewage sludge disposal sites (Mossa et al., 2017).

2.1.3.2. Nature-Based Solutions

Fungi, Fauna, and Microbial Communities: Enhancing soil health and plant performance through improved nutrient uptake can be significantly achieved by leveraging the role of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (Gianinazzi et al., 2010). Understanding the network properties of soil fungal communities and the impact of environmental and land use factors is crucial for agroecosystem sustainability (Ortiz-Álvarez et al., 2021). Moreover, nematode communities serve as reliable indicators of soil health, with biological practices promoting greater diversity and better soil conditions (Biagini & Zullini, 2008; Narula et al., 2002).

Nature-based solutions create value from underutilized natural resources, enhancing soil health, reducing flood risks, increasing soil moisture, and promoting landscape connectivity (Keesstra et al., 2018). Promoting land cover types like coniferous tree stands in desertification-prone areas can enhance microbial biomass and activity, aiding soil recovery (Rutigliano et al., 2023). Additionally, insights from the XI International Colloquium on Soil Zoology underscore the importance of enhancing soil health and productivity through practices like promoting earthworm activity and understanding microbial dynamics (Haimi & Huhta, 1995).

Incorporating soil sampling time is essential when assessing the impact of agricultural practices on soil microbiota. Variations in tillage and fertilization significantly affect microbial communities, particularly during the maize-growing season, thereby aiding more informed decision-making (Fernandez-Gnecco et al., 2022). Understanding the impact of grassland age and management on soil microbes is also important for maintaining ecosystem resilience (Seaton et al., 2022). The stability of soil bacterial communities is closely linked to land use impacts. Soils experiencing low human inputs, such as cork-oak forests and pastures, exhibit more stable bacterial communities compared to those under high human inputs like vineyards and managed meadows (Bevivino et al., 2014). Consequently, tailored soil health-promoting management strategies that consider regional conditions and management intensity levels can positively influence soil microbial communities, enhancing agricultural sustainability, for example, across diverse agro-ecological gradients (Barreiro et al., 2022). These strategies should be developed based on soil type to sustain soil quality and associated ecosystem services, particularly in vulnerable agroecosystems (Salomé et al., 2016).

Nature-based Management Practices: Several strategies and practices are needed to support beneficial soil organisms, combat soilborne diseases, and enhance overall soil health. Organic farming practices in rainfed olive plantations reduce soil erosion and runoff while maintaining crop yields (Zuazo et al., 2020). These practices improve soil physical and biological properties (Şeker et al., 2017), shift nematode community compositions (Quist et al., 2016) and increase microbial biomass (Mantoni et al., 2021). Organic practices enhance labile soil organic matter fractions, combating organic matter depletion by introducing beneficial microorganisms and diverse crops (Murindangabo et al., 2023; Symochko et al., 2023).

Strategies such as host resistance, grafting, biofumigation, and non-chemical control methods effectively combat soilborne diseases in the vegetable sector (Colla et al., 2012). In vineyards and olive orchards, organic practices promote soil health by supporting beneficial organisms like entomopathogenic nematodes (Blanco-Pérez et al., 2022; Campos-Herrera et al., 2021; Montes-Borrego et al., 2013). Moreover, the interaction between soil water availability and phosphorus fertilization affects microbial communities and crop productivity, necessitating adaptive management strategies (Randall et al., 2020).

2.1.4. Archetype 4- Substitute with Conservation (Best Management) Practices

This soil-health-based SBM archetype is based on developing Best Management Practices and conservation agricultural practices, which are central to promoting soil health, enhancing crop productivity, and mitigating environmental impacts. Ecosystems naturally rely on practices such as soil cover, reduced tillage, crop rotation, agroforestry, and grazing to maintain balance and productivity. Farmers can adopt these solutions to leverage unique benefits, often overlapping to provide comprehensive improvements in soil quality and ecosystem sustainability. This approach not only enhances soil structure and reduces erosion but also decreases costs and improves crop resilience.

- ✚ **Value Proposition:** Maintaining and improving soil health and ecosystem services through the adoption of specific conservation practices over conventional methods.
- ✚ **Value Creation & Delivery:** Implementing soil cover, reduced tillage, crop rotation, grazing, and agroforestry provides multiple soil and ecosystem benefits.
- ✚ **Value Capture:** Enhanced soil structure, reduced erosion, reduced costs, and improved crop resilience are key benefits. Agriculturalists capture efficiency gains, while positive externalities can be monetized through government payments, subsidy schemes, certifications, and increased product prices.
- ✚ **Key Targeted Stakeholders:** Farmers/agriculturists, agri-food companies, agri-technology providers, agricultural consultants, and policymakers.

2.1.4.1. Soil Cover and Mulching

Implementing soil cover methods like rolled rye mulch for weed suppression in organic no-tillage soybeans (Smith et al., 2011) and using cover crops (Hao et al., 2023) significantly enhance soil health. Soil cover supports the development of suppressive soils that protect crops against pathogens (Löbmann et al., 2016), demonstrating the multifaceted benefits of continuous soil cover. Conservation

efforts like field margin strips and establishing arable plant sanctuaries contribute to maintaining and improving soil health and biodiversity (Bergmeier et al., 2021). Cover crops mitigate climate change impacts on soil erosion (Panagos et al., 2021), increase earthworm abundance, suppress weeds (Crotty & Stoate, 2019), retain soil moisture, and protect against erosion. Tailored management strategies, including radish cover crops, increase earthworm abundance and suppress weeds (Crotty & Stoate, 2019). In almond orchards, legume cover crops improve soil health and almond quality (Cárceles Rodríguez et al., 2023); improved management practices in young almond orchards enhance sustainability and increase almond production (Mirás-Avalos et al., 2022). In addition, groundcover mulching in Mediterranean vineyards (Raffa et al., 2021) improves soil organic matter, nitrogen availability, and biological health.

2.1.4.2. Reduced Tillage

Reduced tillage practices, such as no-till and chisel ploughing, enhance SOC concentration (Hazarika et al., 2009) and carbon sequestration (Mazzoncini et al., 2016). Transitioning from conventional tillage to no-tillage systems conserves SOC, reduces carbon emissions, and offers economic benefits (Minnikova et al., 2022). Conservation tillage increases soil carbon, enzyme activities, and nutrient concentrations, promoting sustainable nutrient management in maize cultivation (Nugroho et al., 2023). Reduced tillage also maintains microbial activity and improves soil health indicators, contributing to long-term agricultural sustainability (Acir et al., 2022).

2.1.4.3. Crop Rotations

Crop rotation is key to maintaining soil health and reducing disease risks. Rotating crops balances soil fungi and reduces pathogen prevalence (Manici & Caputo, 2009). Diversified rotations, such as those in tomato-based systems, improve microbial activity and soil respiration (Kayikcioglu et al., 2020). Furthermore, incorporating legumes and other subsidiary crops into rotations manages nematode populations and improves soil structure (Schmidt et al., 2017).

2.1.4.4. Agroforestry

Agroforestry systems, which integrate trees and shrubs into agricultural landscapes, provide substantial ecological benefits, including mitigating soil erosion, enhancing SOC, and improving biodiversity (Brunori et al., 2020; Kay et al., 2019). For example, afforestation with black locust improves soil physical and chemical properties (Bolat et al., 2016). Agroforestry practices also maintain understorey biodiversity, naturally controlling pests like the olive fruit fly (Stavrianakis et al., 2023).

2.1.4.5. Grazing and Grassland Management

Regenerative rotational grazing enhances soil carbon storage and grass production without compromising ecosystem services (Díaz de Otálora et al., 2021).

Alternative grazing systems, such as tracks and rewilding for horses, are found to promote biodiversity and support soil health by providing varied habitats and reducing soil compaction (Furtado et al., 2022). Similarly, mixed sheep and cattle grazing improves soil bulk density and enhances ecosystem services like water flow regulation (Jordon, 2021). Besides, embracing pasture-fed livestock farming improves grassland management, increasing biodiversity and soil health (Norton et al., 2022). Additionally, regular management of grasslands on hilly terrains prevents the spread of low-value plants, ensuring the preservation of beneficial grasses and effectively controlling erosion (Skuodienė & Matyžiūtė, 2022). Finally, converting arable land to permanent grassland boosts organic matter and biological stability (Horáková et al., 2020), leading to significant increases in SOC levels (Wenzel et al., 2022).

2.2. Social-Organizational Dimension

This SBM dimension focuses on developing soil-health-related practices and innovations by addressing relevant social-organizational sustainability facets. The three archetypes identified and discussed within this dimension are “Scan, Learn, and Integrate Soil Science” (Archetype 5), “Facilitate Sustainability Transitions” (Archetype 6), and “Encourage Sufficiency and Consider Cultural Values” (Archetype 7). Each archetype begins with a concise summary that introduces the value components and key stakeholders, tailored to the specific context of soil health with a concentration on societal and structural dynamics. Policymakers play a crucial role in this dimension by creating supportive policies, fostering collaboration among stakeholders, and driving the adoption of sustainable soil-health practices.

2.2.1. Archetype 5- Scan, Learn, and Integrate Soil Science

This soil-health-based SBM archetype emphasizes continuous improvement in soil health monitoring and assessment through learning and integrating the latest research and best practices. By systematically scanning current research, learning from diverse methodologies, and integrating findings into practical soil management and monitoring strategies, farmers and agri-businesses can incrementally enhance soil-ecosystem health. Researchers and policymakers can also contribute to developing more comprehensive soil assessment indicators and programs, as well as setting up broader monitoring regimes. This approach leads to informed decision-making regarding soil health management and sustainable agricultural practices, thereby reducing costs and increasing efficiency in the European soil management system.

- ✚ **Value Proposition:** Improving soil-ecosystem health management incrementally through the continuous integration of tools and best practices.
- ✚ **Value Creation & Delivery:** Utilizing soil health indicators and monitoring/assessment techniques, and integrating new research findings into soil management strategies.
- ✚ **Value Capture:** Informed decision-making, optimized land management, and improved sustainable agricultural practices. Farmers capture value from reduced costs and benefit from more efficient practices.
- ✚ **Key Targeted Stakeholders:** Farmers/agriculturists, researchers/soil scientists, agricultural consultants, and policymakers.

2.2.1.1. Soil Health Indicators, Monitoring Techniques, and Informed Decision-making

Soil Health Indicators and Monitoring Techniques: Enhancing soil health is possible through sustainable land management by optimizing physical, chemical, and biological aspects to minimize external inputs and maximize ecosystem services. Evaluating soil health and detecting degradation rely on various soil quality indicators and metrics (Griffiths et al., 2018). Pulido et al. (2017) highlight indicators such as cation exchange capacity, soil organic matter, and soil depth, while Lebert et al. (2007) emphasize soil compaction indicators like “pre-compression stress” and “loading ratio.” Additionally, macro-invertebrates and the IBQS provide integrative measures of soil quality for short- or long-term monitoring (Nuria et al., 2011). Asensio et al. (2013) propose a three-tier approach to classify soils as harmful, unhealthy, or healthy based on their ecological health status.

Microbial Communities and Bio-indicators: Soil microbial communities and bio-indicators are important for understanding soil health and sustainable productivity (Montanarella, 2008). Seasonal and compositional shifts in these communities, influenced by land use and soil management practices, serve as important indicators of soil health. Bevivino et al. (2014) explore these shifts in Mediterranean

ecosystems, identifying bacterial bio-indicators crucial for monitoring soil health. Hontoria et al. (2019) examine the impact of cover crop species on microbial communities, while Federico et al. (2020) identify erosion indicators in forest soil management.

Soil Quality Assessment Methods: Diverse methods for soil quality assessment are essential for sustainable land management. Askari et al. (2015) propose rapid, low-cost, and high-frequency monitoring approaches for agricultural settings. Comprehensive frameworks like the Soil Management Assessment Framework (SMAF) (Andrea et al., 2018) provide a holistic view of soil quality and guide optimal soil and plant management practices (Canfora et al., 2014). Indicators such as soil water retention curves are also crucial for assessing soil quality (Guzmán et al., 2019). Additionally, addressing challenges like plastic pollution in soils requires holistic approaches, as emphasized by Stubenrauch & Ekardt (2020).

Recent Research Insights and Initiatives: Integrating recent research findings and technological advancements can significantly improve soil health management. Studies on thinning practices in forests (Federico et al., 2020), topsoil zinc concentrations in Europe (Van Eynde et al., 2023), and ecoacoustic methods for biodiversity monitoring (Robinson et al., 2023) offer valuable insights. Frameworks for regenerative agriculture (Schreefel et al., 2022), the Land Degradation Neutrality (LDN) indicator (Thomas et al., 2023), and the UK Crop Microbiome Cryobank (UKCMC) project (Ryan et al., 2023) contribute to comprehensive soil health assessment.

Practitioners can leverage findings from research on sustainable pest control for strawberry farming (Amyotte & Samtani, 2023), rapid evidence assessments for agricultural tools (Green et al., 2023), and commercial soil mapping services for grassland nutrient management (Rhymes et al., 2023). These insights support informed decision-making for optimized land management and sustainable agricultural practices (Csikós et al., 2023; Feeney et al., 2023). Moreover, research on winter cover crops' effects on soil health and nitrous oxide emissions (Liu et al., 2022) provides valuable data for improving agricultural sustainability. Integrating these practical applications helps practitioners enhance soil health and productivity effectively.

2.2.1.2. Technological Advancements in Soil Health Assessment

Advanced Soil Health Monitoring Techniques: Technological advancements have revolutionized soil health monitoring. Techniques such as Near Infrared Spectroscopy (NIRS) and multi-nutrient 0.01 M CaCl₂ extraction provide rapid and comprehensive assessments of soil fertility (Reijneveld et al., 2022). Integrating Earth Observation techniques, geostatistical techniques and GIS with in situ sampling enables cost-effective and accurate monitoring of SOC stocks (Andries et al., 2021). Furthermore, utilizing geostatistical techniques and GIS to analyze soil organic matter (SOM) can identify areas with low SOM, guiding regional planning and sustainable management practices in line with European Common Agricultural Policy objectives (Marchetti et al., 2012).

Machine Learning and Innovative Assessment Tools: Machine learning models play a significant role in predicting stable SOC fractions, and improving soil health monitoring and carbon cycle models (Cécillon et al., 2021). Practical tools like the Open Soil Index (OSI) offer farmers and practitioners a framework for assessing soil health and tailoring sustainable farming practices (Ros et al., 2022). AI-generated soil maps from the Soil Data Cube further enhance field management by providing high-resolution estimates of SOC and clay content (Samarinas et al., 2023).

2.2.2. Archetype 6- Facilitate Sustainability Transition

This soil-health-based SBM archetype addresses the sustainability transition in soil health and agriculture, essential for long-term agricultural resilience and environmental health. It focuses on developing supportive policies, collaborative platforms, and holistic approaches to drive the adoption of sustainable practices in Europe. Overcoming macro-level challenges (e.g., political, social, economic) is crucial to encouraging and supporting farmers in this transition. Co-creation of value, social networking among farmers, and the role of policymakers as key stakeholders are pivotal in this social-organizational archetype.

- 🚩 **Value Proposition:** Advancing soil-ecosystem health through harmonized practices and collaborations, supported by policy and stakeholder engagement.
- 🚩 **Value Creation and Delivery:** Advocating for the European soil health laws/policies, participating in collaborative learning and knowledge-sharing, and adopting sustainable practices supported by macro-level initiatives.
- 🚩 **Value Capture:** Improved soil health management, increased compliance with sustainable development goals, and enhanced environmental resilience. Farmers capture value from their contribution to the sustainability transition through mechanisms such as government incentives, market-based schemes, and community recognition.
- 🚩 **Key Targeted Stakeholders:** Policymakers, living Lab and lighthouse coordinators, farmers/agriculturists, researchers/soil scientists, and environmental organizations/NGOs.

2.2.2.1. Compliance with Policies, Schemes, and Strategies

For sustainable soil management practices to improve, various policy frameworks and measures must be implemented. A key move would be to call for a legally binding EU-wide Soil Health Law. This particular law will ensure that soil biodiversity is protected uniformly, bring together beneficial land management practices through incentive-based instruments as well as aid in creating predictive models for addressing spatiotemporal variability of soil biodiversity (Königer et al., 2022).

Moreover, the European Green Deal goals go hand in hand with sustainable practices in soil management based on the principles of the 2030 Biodiversity

Strategy, Farm to Fork strategy and the European Climate Law. Incorporating crop protection measures into the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) of the EU could also contribute to addressing the problem of the projected growth of soil erosion rates by 2050 as a result of climate change and land use (Panagos et al., 2021). These measures include a reduction in the use of chemical pesticides and fertilisers, the conservation of wetlands, the enhancement of SOC, the expansion of organic farming, and the promotion of land restoration initiatives (Montanarella & Panagos, 2021).

Further, policies such as the Biodiversity 2030, Farm to Fork, Chemicals Strategies, Circular Economy Action Plan, European Climate Law, Fit for 55 package, Zero Pollution Action Plan, and EU Soil Strategy for 2030 are essential considerations for maintaining soil health and productivity (Panagos et al., 2022). Agri-environment schemes (AES) in the European Union also play a key role in mitigating environmental impacts and enhancing soil health. However, these schemes should be tailored to individual farming contexts for effective policy targeting and improved ecosystem service provision (Stetter et al., 2022). The Horizon Europe Mission 'A Soil Deal for Europe' and proposed directives like the Soil Monitoring Law offer opportunities for contributing to soil protection, restoration, and sustainable use (Arias-Navarro et al., 2023).

Policies should also facilitate the adoption of regenerative agriculture practices to improve environmental performance across diverse farming systems (Schreefel et al., 2022). To facilitate the adoption of sustainable practices, there is a need for tailored soil management approaches based on soil-specific characteristics. This approach can enhance soil health and quality, contributing to the achievement of sustainable development goals and objectives outlined in the EU Green Deal (Bonfante et al., 2020). Additionally, implementing an Organic Stewardship Scheme under Rural Development Regulation can aid the transition to organic farming, promoting sustainable agriculture in diversified rural economies (O'riordan & Cobb, 2001). Furthermore, the resurgence of legumes in UK agriculture, driven by environmental concerns, marks a shift from monoculture systems towards crop diversification, requiring political and economic support for sustainable transitions (Cusworth et al., 2021). Aligning agricultural policies to prevent or reduce soil erosion is also important for maintaining soil health and productivity (Lugato et al., 2016). Besides, facilitating sustainable cultivation systems and management strategies in bioenergy cropping is recommended to mitigate negative impacts on soil health, particularly in the face of climate change (Ruf et al., 2021).

2.2.2.2. Collaborative Learning and Knowledge-Sharing Platforms, Programs, and Services

Collaborating with (local) stakeholders and integrating their knowledge with experimental research is advised towards sustainable agricultural development (Allan et al., 2013). Multi-stakeholder platforms and agroecological inputs can overcome economic constraints and knowledge gaps, enabling a transition, e.g. from pesticide-heavy practices to agroecological methods (Boulestreau et al., 2021). Hence, promoting collaborative farming networks and knowledge-sharing platforms can significantly enhance collective capacity in soil management (Skaalsveen et al., 2020). Living Labs and Lighthouse farms are exemplary collaborative platforms that foster innovation and sustainable soil management

practices (Löbmann et al., 2022; Mason et al., 2023). These platforms facilitate joint learning among farmers, researchers, and stakeholders to achieve land-related UN SDGs and EU Green Deal objectives by 2030 (Bouma et al., 2022a, b; 2023a). Moreover, participating in soil health monitoring programs, such as earthworm assessments, supports sustainable soil management practices (Stroud, 2019; Stroud & Goulding, 2022). Engaging with initiatives that characterize the density and diversity of bacterial communities in soils is also crucial for assessing microbial biogeography and the impact of land use on soil biodiversity (Ranjard et al., 2010). Likewise, engaging in projects like H3 (Healthy soil, Healthy food, Healthy people) can help transform food systems, focusing on biofortification and reformulating foods to improve nutrition and sustainability (Jackson et al., 2021). Notably, coordinating innovation design across system levels and stakeholders, such as organic mulching cropping systems and crop diversification, supports the agroecological transition of agrifood systems (Boulestreau et al., 2023). Enhancing capacity building in Agricultural Advisory Services (AAS) is needed for providing soil health management advice and supporting the transition to healthy soils (Ingram et al., 2022). Initiatives like the European Society for Soil Conservation (ESSC) provide valuable research, knowledge exchange, and policy guidance to address soil degradation, protection, and conservation (Dazzi et al., 2019).

2.2.2.3. Overcoming the Barriers to Adoption of Sustainable Practices

Understanding the technical, political, social, and economic drivers and barriers to adopting sustainable practices is critical for promoting soil health (Vanino et al., 2023). Recognizing the benefits of these practices and overcoming adoption barriers can further enhance sustainable land use practices (Mosquera-Losada et al., 2023).

Financial constraints, differing priorities, and national insecurity are significant barriers to crop rotation adoption, as seen in Ukraine (Kopytko & Pruneddu, 2018). The resurgence of legumes in UK agriculture, driven by environmental concerns, marks a shift from monoculture systems towards crop diversification and innovation at multiple levels considering the key role of macro-level economic changes, political transitions, and evolving agricultural attitudes (Cusworth et al., 2021). Moreover, miscanthus adoption for sustainable bioenergy in the UK faces challenges such as geography and transport costs, which need to be addressed through cultivar development and improved processing station distribution to contribute to net-zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2050 (von Hellfeld et al., 2022). Decision-makers show high awareness of soil issues, yet the public lacks interest, and national soil protection policies are inconsistent. Stronger stakeholder commitment is needed, along with advocating for a European Soil Directive to improve soil health and conservation efforts (Dumitraşcu et al., 2019). Recognizing the varied stakeholders in sustainable soil management, including value chain participants, environmentally engaged actors, and policymakers, is fundamental for effective decision-making. The Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) helps prioritize criteria, revealing differing interests and power dynamics (Kik et al., 2021). Encouraging European farmers to prioritize the multi-functionality of soils beyond primary productivity is also essential. However, it is key to address challenges like insufficient proof of soil degradation, limited awareness of soil function synergies,

lack of ecosystem service remuneration, inadequate support, and lack of incentives and regulations on soil management (Schröder et al., 2020).

Understanding cognitive lock-ins in farmers' decision-making processes reveals significant barriers to adopting sustainable agricultural practices like crop diversification with legumes (Weituschat et al., 2022). Facilitating agroecological practices within conventional production systems can enhance farmers' connection to nature and promote sustainable agriculture transitions (Giagnocavo et al., 2022). Farmers with a strong entrepreneurial identity, such as those involved in the privately led Carta del Mulino contract farming scheme in Italy, are notably more likely to adopt sustainable practices (Rossi et al., 2023).

To address the above-mentioned barriers, a comprehensive approach is necessary. This includes understanding socio-technical settings and providing adequate support, incentives, and educational initiatives to promote sustainable soil management among farmers (Vanino et al., 2023). Prioritizing research on soil carbon stocks, soil degradation, and fertility is crucial for closing gaps in sustainable soil management. Specifically, to support sustainable practices, it is recommended to enhance research transfer to practitioners, strengthen knowledge brokers, promote peer-to-peer communication and targeted advice, and develop models and monitoring programs (Avasiloaiei et al., 2023; Thorsøe et al., 2023). Additionally, evaluating soil characteristics, harmonization procedures, and increased cooperation among countries at the European scale are essential for developing policies, certifications, and indicators for sustainable soil management and agricultural practices (Bebber, 2023; Cornu et al., 2023; Günal et al., 2015).

Soil health initiatives and robust monitoring systems can significantly improve agricultural productivity and mitigate climate change (McGuire et al., 2022). Besides, adopting the soil security concept as a roadmap for sustainable development can guide stakeholders in balancing ecosystem services, supporting the UN's SDGs, and achieving the objectives of the European Union's Green Deal (Bouma, 2020). Integrating these insights and strategies facilitates a holistic approach to sustainable agriculture, enhancing environmental, social, and economic outcomes.

2.2.3. Archetype 7- Encourage Sufficiency and Consider Cultural Values

This soil-health-based SBM archetype emphasizes incorporating cultural values and encouraging sufficiency for sustainability in natural resources, agriculture, and food. It focuses on improving food systems and promoting soil-care practices that align with cultural and environmental values. By integrating socio-cultural strategies and increasing fruit and vegetable production, this approach supports soil nutrient supply and future crop yields. Policymakers play a key role as essential stakeholders, fostering policies that support these sustainable practices.

- ✚ **Value Proposition:** Enhancing soil protection, farm-human connection, and food productivity, supported by cultural values and interdisciplinary collaboration.
- ✚ **Value Creation & Delivery:** Implementing soil and food socio-cultural strategies and practices, increasing fruit and vegetable production, maintaining soil nutrient supply and increasing food production for future crops.
- ✚ **Value Capture:** Improved soil fertility, better nutrition and human health, and reduced food losses. Farmers capture value through mechanisms such as community recognition, government incentives, and supporting policies that incorporate the cultural and natural heritage value of soils.
- ✚ **Key Targeted Stakeholders:** Policymakers, agri-food companies, and farmers/agriculturists.

Addressing sustainable soil and agricultural practices requires a multifaceted approach that integrates historical insights, cultural values, and contemporary policy frameworks. Understanding and mitigating food losses and waste (FLW) in primary production, as mandated by the EU Waste Framework Directive, is crucial for enhancing farm sustainability and food production potential. By prioritizing mitigation efforts in key sectors such as horticulture and addressing causes like pests and unharvestable produce, significant reductions in FLW can be achieved, thereby improving long-term agricultural sustainability (O'Connor et al., 2022). Additionally, recognizing the historical significance of soil fertility for human health, nutrition, and economic prosperity provides valuable lessons. Learning from past strategies employed by farmers to sustain soil health and adapting these methods to modern contexts can help maintain soil nutrient supply and increase food productivity for future crops (Güldner et al., 2021).

Embracing the spiritual dimensions of soil care within biodynamic agriculture fosters a deeper connection with soils, acknowledging more-than-human agency and fostering reciprocity between soil biota and humans. This approach enriches the understanding and care of soils, offering an alternative framework that extends beyond solely technoscientific methods (Pigott, 2021). Furthermore, recognizing the cultural and natural heritage value of soils, often overlooked in current policies, is essential. Strategies to promote soil protection should include incorporating soil profiles into heritage inventories and leveraging research programs like Horizon Europe and initiatives such as Natura 2000. These efforts can enhance soil literacy

and encourage interdisciplinary collaboration for holistic soil health management (Costantini, 2023).

Addressing stakeholder perceptions of sustainability within food systems, such as those in Sweden, reveals a wide range of views, from reducing meat consumption and food waste to advocating for organic farming and self-sufficiency. These diverse perspectives present both challenges and opportunities for system transformation. Promoting healthy diets, increasing fruit and vegetable production, and building trust among stakeholders can serve as entry points for broader systemic changes. By understanding and addressing these varying viewpoints, a more sustainable and resilient agricultural system can be fostered (Röös et al., 2023).

2.3. Economic Dimension

This SBM dimension focuses on the economic aspect of soil health practices and innovations. The two archetypes identified and discussed within this dimension are “Create Inclusive Value through Innovative Approaches” (Archetype 8) and “Develop Diversified and Productive Solutions” (Archetype 9). Each archetype begins with a concise summary that introduces the value components and key stakeholders, tailored to the specific context of soil health with a concentration on long-term collaborative innovations, diversification and integration of conservation practices, incorporation of technological advancements, and extension of sources for income and investment.

2.3.1. Archetype 8- Create Inclusive Value through Innovative Approaches

This soil-health-based SBM archetype emphasizes integrating advanced strategies, collaborative efforts, and innovative practices to boost soil health, optimize economic gains, and promote sustainability across value chains. The emphasis is on creating value through the involvement and contribution of diverse stakeholders, including policymakers, agri-food companies, farmers, and agri-technology providers. This approach aims to reduce resource use and costs while increasing collaborative synergies.

- ✚ **Value Proposition:** Enhancing soil-health-based ecosystem services, efficiency, and value chain economic benefits, supported by innovative approaches and long-term engagement of diverse stakeholders.
- ✚ **Value Creation & Delivery:** Implementing nutrient stewardship, adopting soil-health-related food innovations, and integrating land management practices within long-term business plans and living labs. This collaborative approach benefits all stakeholders in the long run by developing strategic innovations in agricultural value chains.
- ✚ **Value Capture:** Reduced resource consumption and costs (inclusive economic gains), increased value chain synergy, and improved food supply and benefits.
- ✚ **Key Targeted Stakeholders:** Living Lab and lighthouse coordinators, Agri-food companies, Farmers/agriculturists, agri-technology providers, and policymakers.

Phosphorus (P) fertilizers, initially introduced to enhance agricultural productivity and profitability, now aim to achieve additional goals, such as minimizing water quality impacts, increasing recycling, reducing resource consumption, improving soil health, and enhancing biodiversity. The science of 4R nutrient stewardship addresses these multifaceted objectives. By adapting practices to regional differences in phosphorus surplus and collaborating with scientists and industry stakeholders, agricultural productivity and profitability can be maximized while simultaneously improving water quality, soil health, and biodiversity. This targeted nutrient management approach ensures inclusive economic gains without compromising environmental integrity (Bruulsema et al., 2019).

Developing and integrating soil-health-focused land management practices within long-term business plans and living labs is another critical aspect of sustainable soil management and economic outcomes. These practices support sustainable agriculture in alignment with the UN SDGs and the EU Green Deal, ensuring that sustainable practices are economically viable and beneficial for all stakeholders in the long run (Bouma et al., 2021).

Additionally, forecasting and adopting upcoming food innovations such as plant-based meat alternatives, personalized nutrition, regenerative agriculture, urban agriculture, and packaging innovations are other components of this SBM

archetype. These innovations promote human health, food security, and environmental sustainability, offering valuable insights for advancing food innovation development along the agricultural value chain. This proactive approach ensures that the agricultural sector remains competitive, economically resilient, and inclusive (Zickafoose et al., 2022).

Finally, prioritizing understanding soil health, proactive monitoring, and engaging with government agencies to address climate change challenges through sustainable land management practices is necessary. These practices are influenced by factors such as efficiency, cost reduction, regulations, and market demand, which are key for maintaining economic stability and growth within the agricultural sector. This ensures that the benefits are inclusive and far-reaching (Feliciano, 2022).

2.3.2. Archetype 9- Develop Diversified and Productive Solutions

This soil-health-based SBM archetype emphasizes diverse and integrated solutions to improve soil health, ecosystem services, and agricultural benefits, contributing to sustainable development goals. Through a business lens, it guides European farmers and practitioners towards developing diversified, integrative, and productive solutions. Aligned with SBM literature, it highlights that integrative practices and diversified (innovative) solutions yield more prosperous economic outcomes than solitary efforts (Archetype 4). Diversified farming reduces profit loss risks from market fluctuations and yields better financial outcomes, while promoting sustainable livelihoods, nutritious diets, biodiversity conservation, and climate mitigation (Sánchez et al. 2022).

- ✚ **Value Proposition:** Enhancing soil health, ecosystem services, productivity, and economic benefits through diversified conservation practices and innovative solutions.
- ✚ **Value Creation & Delivery:** Implementing integrated soil and crop management practices, incorporating technological advancements, and agroecological methods.
- ✚ **Value Capture:** Boosted productivity, crop production, and recreational access, as well as increased bilateral products/services. Farmers capture value through reduced costs, enhanced crop yields, and increased sources of income. Mechanisms such as government incentives, market-based schemes, and community recognition support these outcomes further.
- ✚ **Key Targeted Stakeholders:** Farmers/agriculturists, agri-tech providers, agricultural consultants, and agri-food companies.

2.3.2.1. Integrated Soil and Crop Management Practices

Improving Soil Health and Ecosystem Services: Adopting integrated soil management practices is crucial for improving soil health and ecosystem services.

A wide range of studies in the European context highlight the importance of integrative and diversified approaches. These include enhancing Integrated Pest Management (IPM) practices and extensive cultivation practices in orchards (Biasi et al., 2021; Daelemans et al., 2022), organic production systems for almonds (Cárceles Rodríguez et al., 2023), integrating hydropedology with soil physics and pedology (Bouma, 2023b), and aligning soil health management with UN SDGs and EU Green Deal objectives (Bouma et al., 2021).

Strategies such as utilizing diverse plant communities, including legume-based cover crops, help optimize multiple ecosystem services like soil fertility, weed suppression, and support of beneficial invertebrates (Williams et al., 2020; Storkey et al., 2015). Similarly, integrating winter crops like *Lupinus albus* alongside summer crops such as industrial hemp enhances soil recovery during phytoextraction, serving as green manure, promoting bacterial growth, and increasing metal bioavailability, which minimizes the need for chemical amendments and enhances ecological and human health safety (Fumagalli et al., 2014).

Additionally, diverse soil and crop management practices, including cover crops, animal manure, and crop sequences, contribute to maintaining good soil quality over the long term, with practices like grass-clover incorporation in organic systems improving aggregate stability and increasing earthworm density (De Notaris et al., 2021). Integrating legume/cereal ground cover crops in organic olive orchards can enhance parasitic wasp activity for effective pest control while minimizing impact on non-target invertebrates (Volakakis et al., 2022). Moreover, Soil Improving Cropping Systems (SICS) focus on cover crops, mulching, soil compaction alleviation, and minimum tillage to mitigate soil erosion and increase SOC stocks, particularly in central European cropping areas (Bartman et al., 2022). Integrating landscape ecology approaches to predict the effects of land management on soil health and crop yield further enhances the understanding and implementation of these strategies (Stockdale et al., 2019).

Implementing herbicide-free no-till systems in agriculture remains challenging, as reducing tillage tends to increase herbicide use and eliminating tillage significantly impacts weed management, leading to yield loss. Diverse crop rotations and cover cropping are vital for managing weeds while reducing tillage and herbicide use, though no tested system achieves all three objectives simultaneously (Colbach & Cordeau, 2022). In addition, harnessing hedgerows for diverse benefits in agriculture includes biodiversity conservation, climate change mitigation, soil health, human health, well-being, and livelihoods. Research calls for policy and political measures to promote sustainable management of hedgerows and integrate them into agroecological frameworks to maximize their potential for ecosystem services delivery (Tilzey, 2021).

Benefits through Crop Rotations and Diversification: Promoting strategic choices such as land renting and soil health-improving crop rotations can mitigate the negative economic impacts of environmentally oriented production systems (Rossing et al., 1997). On the same note, integrating perennial grains, particularly intermediate wheatgrass, into Western European farming systems addresses environmental challenges associated with traditional cereal grain production, enhancing soil health, water quality, and sustainable cropping systems while improving food security (Duchene et al., 2019).

Further, implementing burial of crop residues and prioritizing two-year rotations with wheat in Mediterranean rainfed conditions have shown higher yields and increased SOC and nitrogen content over 30 years compared to continuous cropping or rotations with higher wheat frequencies (Bonciarelli et al., 2016). Likewise, enhancing soil quality in barley-maize and maize cropping systems by implementing diversified crop rotations and reduced tillage practices promotes beneficial nematofauna composition and improves soil structure, contributing to sustainable agricultural management (Manachini et al., 2009).

Addressing climate change impacts on agriculture and water resources involves enhancing water management, developing climate-resistant crops, and adopting climate-smart agriculture practices (Srivastav et al., 2021). Planning and diversifying crop rotations in response to climate change predictions, as highlighted in a study spanning regions from the south of the UK to the south of France, underscores how farmers utilize rotations and crop diversity to reinforce financial stability and soil health. In parallel, communication framing that encourages environmentally sustainable adaptation strategies is essential (Bane et al., 2021).

Diversifying farming strategies and agricultural systems with structural landscape elements, organic fertilization, and conservation tillage is needed to address soil degradation (Strauss et al., 2023), and enhance soil health (Babin et al., 2019). A broad and integrated approach to conservation agriculture, including cover cropping, crop rotations, and precision farming techniques alongside conservation tillage, achieves soil diversity in semi-arid Mediterranean agroecosystems (Sánchez-Moreno et al., 2018), and greater environmental and economic benefits in intensive arable settings, as demonstrated by studies in the River Wensum Demonstration Test Catchments (DTC) in the UK (Cooper et al., 2020).

Benefits through Perennial and Mixed Cropping Systems: Exploring the integration of perennial wheat genotypes in farming practices leverages the benefits of taller plants, increased tillering, and robust root systems. Despite smaller kernels, the environmental advantages such as higher soil respiration and post-harvest regrowth make perennial wheat valuable. Optimizing field management and breeding strategies enhances agronomic performance and sustainability in wheat production (Baronti et al., 2022). Furthermore, incorporating overwinter cover crops, particularly Brassica compositions, in cereal production systems in regions with short growing seasons increases subsequent spring barley crop yield and nitrogen concentration without compromising soil health or agronomic sustainability (Holland et al., 2021). Additionally, balancing traditional rainfed agriculture with building water reservoirs in southeast Portugal stabilizes the population and boosts agricultural profitability (Esgalhado & Guimaraes, 2020).

Adopting mixed farming systems combining organic farming and grazing enhances soil quality and ecosystem services (Zani et al., 2021). On the same note, transitioning to extensive grazing systems in sheep meat production reduces concentrate reliance and enhances sustainability. Implementing delayed lambing on farms with abundant pastures improves market prices and meat supply. Increasing Norwegian White Sheep lamb production boosts profits and uses homegrown feed, minimizing concentrate use (Bhatti et al., 2020). In addition, implementing instrumented farm-scale trials helps to assess economic-environmental trade-offs in pasture-based ruminant systems (Takahashi et al., 2018).

2.3.2.2. Innovations and Technological Integration

Benefits through Innovative Crop and Soil Management: Integrating legumes into diverse products and farming systems while promoting sustainable food systems, diets, and technology transfer in Europe is crucial for soil health and productivity (Ferreira et al., 2021; Siddique et al., 2012). Moreover, exploring ground vegetation cover options for Mediterranean vineyards affects vine stress, grape yield, and quality. Similarly, implementing cover crop mixtures can increase grape production and quality while managing vine water stress and nutrient status (Raffa et al., 2022). In the same vein, utilizing wheat straw to remediate heavy metal contamination in soils improves soil quality and fertility while reducing toxic metal availability, integrating circular economy principles for added environmental and economic benefits (Golia, 2023). Likewise, novel carbon capture-based organo-mineral fertilizers (CCOMFs) can serve as an alternative to conventional mineral fertilizers, producing comparable crop yields without significant negative impacts on SOC, microbial biomass, pH, nutrient concentrations, or root development, thereby supporting sustainable agricultural practices (Burak & Sakrabani, 2023). Finally, using LiDAR-based tools to minimize nutrient loss and erosion can enhance agricultural planning and soil management (Hayes et al., 2022).

Benefits through Integrated Agroecological Practices and Technologies: Developing integrated agroecological farming practices in landscapes utilizing large herbivores promotes conservation, agriculture, and human activities simultaneously. These systems benefit habitat and species diversity, soil health, food production, education, and recreational access, thus supporting the needs of both people and nature in shared landscapes (Balfour et al., 2021). On a similar note, redesigning Swedish farm systems to envision farmland as carbon sinks involves integrating perennial crops, keyline design, and soil health awareness, thereby enhancing farmer income and health while aligning with consumer demand and agroecological principles (Johansson et al., 2022). Furthermore, optimizing soil management in organic vineyards by selecting floor management treatments such as alternate tillage with temporary cover crops or temporary grass improves vine performance, yield, and grape quality while addressing soil health concerns like nutrient deficiencies and low vigor (Gatti et al., 2022). Additionally, utilizing affordable, user-friendly agricultural technologies improves soil health, moisture management, and crop production. Addressing challenges with these strategies can enhance food availability, while complementary efforts focusing on food safety and nutrition education are crucial for comprehensive food security goals (Hatzenbuehler & Peña-Lévano, 2022).

3. Conclusion

The report develops an integrative soil-health-based SBM approach tailored to the European context, adapting traditional SBM dimensions to emphasize ecosystem services, specific land-use practices, and partnerships for delivering value to stakeholders, including society and the environment. Building on archetypes identified in the literature, the framework integrates economic, environmental-technological, and social-organizational dimensions. A systematic literature review yielded 215 European-focused studies, which were analyzed to formulate SBM archetypes and sub-archetypes, offering practical recommendations for farmers, policymakers, LLs and LHs coordinators, and researchers. Highlighting drivers and barriers to soil health practice adoption, particularly within the "Facilitate Sustainability Transitions" archetype, the report incorporates insights from Dutch arable farmers, underscoring the importance of knowledge sharing and social networks, institutional support, and technical and personal factors (see Annex 2). This comprehensive approach advocates for investments in soil health, promoting sustainable agricultural practices that enhance economic viability and societal well-being.

Practical Implications

The systematic overview of the archetypes in this deliverable highlights that farmers are the primary audience for a soil-health-based SBM approach, playing a crucial role in adopting soil health practices, improving ecosystem services, and benefiting from relevant economic gains. Additionally, policymakers and LL and LH coordinators are essential in facilitating value co-creation and transitioning to advanced levels of soil sustainability, particularly in archetypes 6, 7, and 8. Policymakers are pivotal in encouraging farmers' adoption of soil health practices and enhancing soil health value capture across most archetypes. By promoting collaborative farming networks and knowledge-sharing platforms, they can significantly enhance collective capacity in soil management. LLs and LHs exemplify these collaborative platforms, fostering innovation and sustainable soil management practices, and facilitating joint learning among farmers, researchers, and stakeholders. This collaborative approach contributes to the achievement of land-related UN Sustainable Development Goals and EU Green Deal objectives. Figure 1 illustrates the identified archetypes, classified based on the key roles of the main stakeholders: farmers, policymakers, and coordinators of LLs and LHs.

Figure 1. Recommended Archetypes for Key Stakeholder Groups

Farmers

- Archetypes 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 9

Policy-makers

- Archetype 6
- Archetype 7

LL and LH coordinators

- Archetype 6
- Archetype 8

4. Annex 1. Practical Recommendations for Farmers, Agricultural Practitioners, and Policymakers: Classified by Soil-Health-Based SBM Archetypes

Environmental-Technological Dimension

1. Optimize Use Efficiency

1.1. Water-Use Efficiency and Irrigation Practices

- Evaluate trade-offs of transitioning from flood to drip irrigation (DI), as DI improves water use efficiency but may reduce soil nutrients away from emitters, to protect soil health and minimize environmental impacts (Puy et al., 2017).
- Use multivariate techniques to analyze irrigation water quality dynamics, identifying key parameters and spatio-temporal variations to enhance crop productivity and soil health while mitigating adverse impacts (Yurtseven et al., 2020).
- Consider using treated wastewater (TW/W) for irrigation, balancing its benefits with potential maize yield losses compared to freshwater (FW) for sustainable water resource management (Kayikcioglu, 2018).
- Assess the impact of irrigation practices on Mediterranean agricultural soils, as drip and sprinkler systems can reduce soil organic matter and increase salinity compared to rainfed systems, and adopt strategies to mitigate these effects (Telo da Gama et al., 2023).

1.2. Nutrient-Use Efficiency

- Keep soil phosphorus (Olsen-P) below 53 mg P kg⁻¹, conduct regular soil testing, and use organic amendments to prevent leaching and minimize environmental impact in the Mediterranean region (Ortiz et al., 2023).
- Enhance nitrogen use efficiency (NUE) through collaborations, optimized fertilizer use, manure management, and improved soil health (Misselbrook et al., 2022).
- Maintain species diversity in mixed pastures by managing pasture height near the critical leaf area index (LAI) and keeping the nitrogen nutrition index (NNI) below 0.8 for grasses (Barreta et al., 2023).

1.3. Land-Use Decisions/Management

- Tailor land-use management practices to habitat types based on soil physicochemical properties to maintain soil carbon levels and pH balance, supporting sustainable agriculture and environmental conservation (Seaton et al., 2021).
- Develop high-resolution SOC maps at the field scale by integrating environmental covariates and crop data to maintain SOC levels and optimize sustainable land use decisions (Zhou et al., 2022).

- Optimize land-use intensity in vulnerable Mediterranean systems to sustain ecosystem services by balancing traditional practices that benefit Holm oak growth and drought resilience against human-induced changes that increase mortality and reduce growth (Gazol et al., 2021).
- Enhance water management, develop climate-resistant crops, and adopt climate-smart practices to address climate change impacts (Srivastav et al., 2021).
- Use rapid evidence assessment to quickly evaluate the environmental costs and benefits of agricultural tools, aiding informed decisions for sustainable practices, such as balancing the benefits of inversion tillage for weed control against its risks to soil health and climate (Green et al., 2023).

2. Reduce/Remediate Emissions and Pollution

2.1. Reduce Emissions

- Reduce greenhouse gas emissions in row-crop agriculture through digital agriculture, crop and microbial genetics, and electrification (Northrub et al., 2021).
- Enhance soil carbon sequestration, minimize fertilizer use, improve soil water management, reduce erosion, and retain nitrogen under warming conditions by using post-legume cover crops (Kaye & Quemada, 2017).
- Implement the "4 per 1000" initiative and negative emission technologies (NETs) with industry collaboration to boost soil carbon sequestration, aiding global climate change mitigation and ecosystem services (Lal, 2020).
- Address climate change and land use impacts on SOC by adopting crop rotation changes and soil management practices to enhance SOC sequestration and preserve existing stocks (Gutierrez et al., 2023).
- Enhance soil quality in mine-impacted regions through phytostabilization with Mediterranean shrubs and liming, focusing on species like *Myrtus communis* and *Retama sphaerocarpa* to reduce labile arsenic levels and increase soil carbon and nitrogen (Moreno-Jiménez et al., 2012).
- Improve soil health and reduce CO₂ emissions using biopreparations like essential oils, plant extracts, marine algae extracts, and microbial agents (*Azotobacter chroococcum*, *Azospirillum brasilense*) to enhance soil porosity and stabilize emissions (Buragiene et al., 2023).

2.2. Mitigate Soil Pollution

- Use low-Cd phosphorus fertilizers, cultivate Cd-resistant crop varieties, promote nutrient use efficiency, and explore soil phytoremediation to mitigate cadmium contamination and reduce human exposure in European agriculture (Suciu et al., 2022).
- Manage sludge and mitigate soil pollution from microplastics through collaboration with multiple stakeholders (Milojevic et al., 2021).
- Use additives like carbon nanotubes and clay to reduce heavy metal mobility in contaminated soils, enhancing soil health and sustainability (Correia et al., 2020).
- Conduct thorough soil mapping and risk assessments in urban areas to protect community health from heavy metal contamination, emphasizing proactive pollution monitoring in urban agriculture and public health (Świdwa-Urbańska & Battle-Sales, 2021).

- Preserve biodiversity and soil functions in urban green spaces by addressing even low pollution levels to prevent soil fauna degradation and ensure sustainable agriculture (Tóth et al., 2023).

3. Foster Natural Cycles

3.1. Organic Amendments (creating value from waste)

- Use compost and pig slurry to enhance soil fertility and reduce waste, contributing to circular economy principles (Pardo et al., 2011).
- Use compost from municipal waste to sustain wheat productivity and soil fertility, as it increases SOC content more effectively than organic commercial fertilizer, despite potential impacts on grain quality, thereby supporting soil health in Mediterranean conditions (Leogrande et al., 2016).
- Utilize spent mushroom substrate as an organic manure for agricultural use, adhering to European Union regulations for winter storage to prevent nutrient runoff. Analyze SMS nutrient content before use due to variability among sources to ensure effective soil structure and quality improvement (Velusami et al., 2021).
- Recognize the positive impact of dung application on soil health in temperate grasslands and prioritize its use to maintain SOC, nitrogen levels, and earthworm abundance, considering soil management history (Segura et al., 2023).
- Adopt alternative management systems with organic fertilization for forage production in dairy farms to improve soil health by increasing earthworm abundance and enhancing soil infiltration compared to conventional methods (Baizán et al., 2021).
- Combine NPK fertilizer with vermicompost and organic mulching to enhance shoot growth and pod yield of beans in mild-tropical climates during the dry season, although it may reduce nodulation due to decreased soil oxygenation (Singh et al., 2011).
- Explore the potential of rabbit manure-derived biochar, especially at lower production temperatures, to enhance soil quality and carbon sequestration in mining soils. This biochar improves soil health by increasing enzyme activities and microbial biomass, offering a sustainable solution for soil remediation (Cárdenas-Aguiar et al., 2022).
- Improve crop productivity and soil health in the Mediterranean region by using biochar from sewage sludge, olive-mill waste, and compost, which sustainably enhances tomato growth. Ensure biochars meet safety standards to optimize soil fertility and yield while minimizing health risks (Lilli et al., 2023).
- Adopt biochar-based smart fertilizers to enhance soil quality and crop productivity sustainably. Collaborate on research and field testing to advance agricultural sustainability practices (Abiola et al., 2023).
- Use recycled bio-based fertilizers (RDF) derived from waste streams to replace conventional phosphorus fertilizers in grasslands. RDF application significantly alters soil microbial and nematode communities, with struvite products yielding the highest crop biomass while maintaining microbial diversity and minimally disturbing nematode communities (Karpinska et al., 2021).

- Consider the benefits of bio-based fertilizers (BBFs) for managing bio-waste and improving soil health, while addressing contamination risks and social acceptance hurdles. Invest in technology development and environmental risk assessments to advance BBF adoption, supporting sustainable agriculture and the circular economy (Kurniawati et al., 2023).
- Use organic amendments and green manure (CONS) to improve soil health and sustainability by boosting SOC, enhancing nitrogen use efficiency, and reducing nitrate leaching, which benefits tomato yield. While synthetic fertilizers (SYN) can increase wheat yield, CONS provides long-term advantages for sustainable farming (Piccini et al., 2023).
- Incorporate crop residues like winter oilseed rape, faba beans, and sawdust to reduce nitrogen losses, improve water quality, and cut greenhouse gas emissions. Prioritize using crop residues from the previous crop for the most effective results, considering amendment type and field conditions (Rothardt & Kage, 2023).
- Maintain SOC levels by returning crop residues and adding manures, boosting SOC to 60-70% of initial values for sustained soil health. Implement sustainable land-use practices to counter rapid SOC loss, especially in tropical climates (Powlson et al., 2022).
- Incorporate organic amendments, especially in woody crops, to boost SOC storage rates (in Mediterranean agricultural soils), aiding in climate change mitigation and adaptation efforts (Francaviglia et al., 2019).
- Implement improved management strategies to expedite recovery and restore productivity after extreme winter flooding (Harvey et al., 2019).
- Integrate drinking-water treatment residuals (DWTR) with lime to improve soil quality and reduce metal extractability in mining-affected soils, supporting plant growth and minimizing ecological risks. Enhance overall soil health with supplemental organic or mineral fertilizers (Alvarenga et al., 2018).
- Utilize ash from residual forest biomass combustion as a sustainable solution for restoring degraded mining soils. Implement ash-based amendments to correct soil pH, reduce metal bioavailability, and enhance soil organism survival and reproduction, ultimately promoting soil health and ecological function recovery in affected areas (Mendes et al., 2021).
- Utilize bio-stabilized material (BSM) from municipal solid wastes as soil amendments in peri-urban vacant lands, combined with *Brassica napus* cultivation, to enhance soil productivity, plant growth, and microbial activity, providing a sustainable solution for ecosystem restoration and circular economy practices in urban fringe areas (Miguez et al., 2020).
- Promote the continued land application of pulp and paper mill sludge (PPMS) as a sustainable agricultural soil amendment (Turner et al., 2022).
- Optimize biosolids application rates to balance nutrient supply and organic matter benefits with potential heavy metal accumulation, ensuring soil microbial diversity and community structure remain optimal for long-term soil health at sewage sludge disposal sites (Mossa et al., 2017).

3.2. Nature-Based Solutions

- Enhance soil health, plant performance, and ecosystem services by improving nutrient uptake through arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (Gianinazzi et al., 2010).
- Consider network properties in understanding the impact of environmental and land use factors on soil fungal communities and agroecosystem sustainability (Ortiz-Álvarez et al., 2021).
- Adopt biological farming practices to enhance soil health and biodiversity, as evidenced by higher nematode diversity and better soil conditions in biologically managed fields (Biagini & Zullini, 2008).
- Consider the impact of fertilizers on soil microbes, with certain fertilizers (e.g., NPK+FYM, NPK) enhancing microbial abundance and supporting soil health (Narula et al., 2002).
- Create value from underutilized natural resources with nature-based solutions to enhance soil health, reduce flood risks, increase soil moisture, and promote landscape connectivity (Keesstra et al., 2018).
- Promote land cover types like coniferous tree stands in desertification-prone areas to enhance microbial biomass and activity, focusing on soil recovery strategies and monitoring changes (Rutigliano et al., 2023).
- Enhance soil health and productivity through practices such as promoting earthworm activity and understanding microbial dynamics (Haimi & Huhta, 1995).
- Incorporate soil sampling time when assessing agricultural practices' impact on soil microbiota, as variations in tillage and fertilization significantly affect microbial communities (Fernandez-Gnecco et al., 2022).
- Maintain grasslands to enhance soil health and ecosystem resilience by understanding how grassland age and management impact soil microbes (Seaton et al., 2022).
- Link land use impacts to soil bacterial community structure, with low human input areas (e.g., cork-oak forest, pasture) exhibiting more stable communities compared to high input areas (e.g., vineyards, managed meadow) (Bevivino et al., 2014).
- Adopt informed soil health-promoting management strategies tailored to regional conditions and management intensity levels to positively influence soil microbial communities and enhance agricultural sustainability (Barreiro et al., 2022).
- Tailor soil management strategies based on soil type to sustain soil quality and ecosystem services in vulnerable agroecosystems (Salomé et al., 2016).
- Reduce soil erosion and runoff, maintain crop yields, and improve soil health through organic and conservation agriculture practices in rainfed olive plantations (Zuazo et al., 2020).
- Improve soil physical and biological properties through sustainable management practices (Şeker et al., 2017).
- Adopt organic farming practices to shift nematode community composition and enhance soil ecosystem functioning (Quist et al., 2016).
- Improve soil health by increasing microbial biomass through organic farming practices (Mantoni et al., 2021).

- Embrace sustainable farming practices to combat organic matter depletion by introducing diverse crops and beneficial microorganisms (Murindangabo et al., 2023).
- Preserve soil organic matter and support essential microorganisms by reducing intensive agricultural practices and long-term mineral fertilizer use (Symochko et al., 2023).
- Combat soilborne diseases in the vegetable sector with strategies such as host resistance, grafting, biofumigation, and non-chemical control methods (Colla et al., 2012).
- Support soil health and beneficial organisms like entomopathogenic nematodes (EPNs) in vineyards through organic practices, fostering EPN activity and offering benefits for pest management (Blanco-Pérez et al., 2022).
- Embrace EPNs for sustainable pest management in viticulture, reducing reliance on agrochemicals and serving as bioindicators of soil health (Campos-Herrera et al., 2021).
- Enhance soil properties and microbial functional diversity in commercial olive orchards through organic management practices (Montes-Borrego et al., 2013).
- Address climate change impacts on soil health by understanding the interaction between soil water availability and phosphorus fertilization to optimize soil bacterial communities and crop productivity (Randall et al., 2020).

4. Substitute with Conservation (Best Management) Practices

4.1. Soil Cover and Mulching

- Use rolled rye mulch to suppress weeds in organic no-tillage soybeans (Smith et al., 2011).
- Integrate cover crops into farming practices to enhance soil structure and enrich SOC content, improving soil quality and productivity (Hao et al., 2023).
- Protect crop plants against pathogens using suppressive soils supported by soil cover and nutrient balance (Löbmann et al., 2016).
- Manage conservation efforts to protect Caucalidion vegetation in Germany's arable landscapes (Bergmeier et al., 2021).
- Manage cover crops and limited soil disturbance to offset climate change impacts on soil erosion, particularly in areas with erosion rates above 5 t ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ (Panagos et al., 2021).
- Manage cover crops with radish to enhance soil health, increase earthworm abundance, and suppress weeds, offering economic benefits for sustainable rotations (Crotty & Stoate, 2019).
- Implement sustainable soil management strategies, such as legume cover crops in almond orchards, to enhance soil health and improve almond quality (Cárceles Rodríguez et al., 2023).
- Prioritize soil quality in young almond orchards and improve management practices to enhance sustainability and maximize production (Mirás-Avalos et al., 2022).

- Improve soil health in Mediterranean vineyards by adopting groundcover mulching practices like pigeon bean or barley-squarrosium clover mixtures to enhance soil organic matter, nitrogen availability, soil structure, and biological health (Raffa et al., 2021).

4.2. Reduced Tillage

- Benefit from no-till and chisel ploughing as they lead to greater SOC concentration in the topsoil compared to mouldboard ploughing (Hazarika et al., 2009).
- Manage no-tillage practices to enhance carbon sequestration and soil health in Mediterranean conditions (Mazzoncini et al., 2016).
- Transition from conventional tillage to no-tillage practices to preserve SOC, reduce carbon emissions, and achieve cost savings, promoting sustainable soil management (Minnikova et al., 2022).
- Implement long-term conservation tillage practices to enhance soil health, increase nutrient supply, and promote sustainable nutrient management in maize cultivation fields (Nugroho et al., 2023).
- Prioritize adopting reduced and no-tillage systems to enhance soil health, preserve SOC, maintain microbial activity, and support sustainable agricultural production (Acir et al., 2022).

4.3. Crop Rotations

- Rotate crops to maintain a healthier balance of soil fungi and reduce the risk of pathogen dominance (Manici & Caputo, 2009).
- Implement diversified tomato-based crop rotations with reduced tillage practices to significantly improve soil health indicators in Mediterranean climates (Kayikcioglu et al., 2020).
- Incorporate specific subsidiary crops in crop rotations to manage plant-parasitic nematode populations effectively, with conservation tillage having minor effects (Schmidt et al., 2017).

4.4. Agroforestry

- Promote agroforestry to mitigate soil erosion, low SOC, water pollution, salinization, climate change impacts, and biodiversity loss (Kay et al., 2019).
- Implement extensive sustainable agricultural practices, including traditional agroforestry methods, to mitigate land degradation and support multipurpose agriculture while preserving ecological services (Brunori et al., 2020).
- Consider afforestation with black locust to improve soil physical and chemical properties, increase SOC and nitrogen content, and enhance microbial biomass and activity, promoting soil improvement and sustainable land management (Bolat et al., 2016).
- Adopt understory biodiversity management in olive groves to naturally control the olive fruit fly, boosting biodiversity and providing effective pest control (Stavrianakis et al., 2023).

4.5. Grazing and Grassland Management

- Implement regenerative rotational grazing in pastures to enhance springtime grass production and topsoil carbon storage without significant trade-offs in other soil ecosystem services (Díaz de Otálora et al., 2021).

- Adopt alternative grazing systems like tracks, Equicentral, and rewilding for horses, ponies, donkeys, and mules to enhance sustainability, support diverse plant life and wildlife, and promote sustainable waste management (Furtado et al., 2022).
- Implement mixed sheep and cattle grazing to improve soil bulk density, enhance soil health, and boost ecosystem services like water flow regulation (Jordon, 2021).
- Embrace pasture-fed livestock farming to improve grassland management, as pasture-fed practices show positive associations with plant diversity and soil health (Norton et al., 2022).
- Manage grassland on hilly terrains regularly to prevent the spread of low-value plants and weeds, preserving beneficial grasses like *Festuca rubra* and controlling erosion (Skuodienė & Matyžiūtė, 2022).
- Consider afforestation and converting arable land to permanent grassland to improve agroecosystems' organic matter and biological stability (Horáková et al., 2020).
- Implement improved soil management practices to significantly increase SOC levels, as demonstrated in grassland and cultivated soils over three decades (Wenzel et al., 2022).

Social-Organizational Dimension

5. Scan, Learn, and Integrate Soil Science

5.1. Soil Health Indicators, Monitoring Techniques, and Informed Decision-making

- Use proxies like earthworm abundance and biodiversity, as demonstrated in water infiltration studies, and transition scientific knowledge into practical applications with robust monitoring services (Griffiths et al., 2018).
- Incorporate specific soil quality indicators such as cation exchange capacity, available potassium, soil organic matter, water content at field capacity, soil depth, and Ah-horizon thickness, along with degradation indicators like bare ground cover percentage and bulk density at 5-10 cm depth to accurately assess and manage soil health (Pulido et al., 2017).
- Implement a comprehensive concept for assessing soil compaction, utilizing indicators such as "pre-compression stress" and "loading ratio" alongside practical guidelines for best management practices, to identify and mitigate harmful subsoil compaction, ensuring sustainable soil management and protection (Lebert et al., 2007).
- Utilize soil macro-invertebrates as integrative measures of soil quality and employ IBQS for short- or long-term monitoring, ensuring calibration and validation based on regional context (Nuria et al., 2011).
- Take a three-tier approach to classify soils as harmful, unhealthy, or healthy based on their ecological health status (Asensio et al., 2013).
- Explore potential bio-indicators to effectively integrate them into soil monitoring activities (Montanarella, 2008).

- Identify bacterial bio-indicators of soil health and sustainable productivity by analyzing seasonal and compositional shifts in soil bacterial communities in response to land use and soil management, particularly in Mediterranean ecosystems (Bevivino et al., 2014).
- Acquire knowledge about cover crop species and their impacts on microbial communities to inform and enhance agricultural practices (Hontoria et al., 2019).
- Evaluate the impact of thinning practices on forest soil by identifying erosion indicators and correlating them with parameters like organic carbon and biological activity, using water-soluble phenols as potential erosion monitors for sustainable management (Federico et al., 2020).
- Implement reliable and efficient approaches for monitoring and evaluating soil quality, enabling rapid, low-cost, and high-frequency assessments in agricultural settings (Askari et al., 2015).
- Integrate comprehensive soil health assessment frameworks like the Soil Management Assessment Framework (SMAF) into agroecosystem assessments to identify optimal soil management practices, delivering multiple ecosystem services and promoting ecological intensification in agriculture, as demonstrated by Italian case studies (Andrea et al., 2018).
- Enhance environmental risk assessments (ERA) for genetically modified plants (GMPs) by considering plant identity, growth, soil characteristics, and climate on microbial diversity. Use comprehensive soil analyses to establish baseline data and evaluate GMP effects on soil microbial communities (Canfora et al., 2014).
- Utilize water-related properties, such as the soil water retention curve, to assess soil quality, as changes in management practices significantly impact soil properties; this underscores the efficacy of water retention curves in detecting soil health changes and suggests opportunities for refining assessment tools (Guzmán et al., 2019).
- Address plastic pollution in agricultural soils with a multifaceted approach that includes comprehensive quantity-control instruments, as proposed in climate protection laws, to effectively mitigate threats to soil health and fertility (Stubenrauch & Ekardt, 2020).
- Utilize recent research on topsoil zinc concentrations in Europe, informed by machine learning models, to assess eco-toxicological risks and zinc deficiency areas, guiding soil management and crop nutrition strategies for improved productivity and environmental health (Van Eynde et al., 2023).
- Incorporate ecoacoustic methods for monitoring belowground biodiversity during restoration efforts, as research indicates their effectiveness in enhancing biodiversity monitoring and supporting ecosystem recovery across various landscapes (Robinson et al., 2023).
- Embrace modelling frameworks designed for effective implementation of regenerative agriculture practices, considering trade-offs and potential benefits like improved climate regulation and soil health (Schreefel et al., 2022).

- Apply the Land Degradation Neutrality (LDN) indicator with comprehensive methods, including field surveys and sub-indicators for erosion and critical load exceedance, and incorporate soil health metrics such as bulk density and contamination thresholds to ensure a thorough assessment and prevent overlooking degradation in regulating and supporting ecosystem services (Thomas et al., 2023).
- Leverage the UK Crop Microbiome Cryobank (UKCMC) project to access microbiome data for key UK crops. This resource supports research to enhance soil and crop health, promoting sustainable agriculture and improving crop management practices (Ryan et al., 2023).
- Gain insights into advanced breeding, automated production, and sustainable pest control for strawberry farming (Amyotte & Samtani, 2023).
- Utilize commercial soil mapping services for grassland nutrient management with caution, as their accuracy varies; while effective for predicting soil organic matter, other nutrients like pH, P, K, and Mg may be less reliable. Certification and rigorous validation are essential to ensure data accuracy and build farmer trust before widespread adoption (Rhymes et al., 2023).
- Leverage methodologies to gain insights into soil biomass productivity, aiding informed decision-making for optimized land management. Utilize productivity indices to tailor farming practices, improve sustainability, and align with broader agricultural goals (Csikós et al., 2023).
- Benefit from established target values for soil properties in Great Britain's landscapes. These benchmarks, derived from national topsoil data, guide landowners in assessing soil health and making informed decisions to improve soil quality and productivity (Feeney et al., 2023).
- Stay updated on the evolving research landscape regarding cover crops' environmental impacts, particularly focusing on topics such as winter cover crops' effects on soil health and their impact on nitrous oxide emissions (Liu et al., 2022).

5.2. Technological Advancements in Soil Health Assessment

- Manage soil testing by adopting broad-spectrum methods like Near Infrared Spectroscopy (NIRS) and multi-nutrient 0.01 M CaCl₂ extraction. These techniques provide rapid, comprehensive assessments of soil characteristics, enabling more sustainable soil management practices and cropping systems (Reijneveld et al., 2022).
- Combine Earth Observation techniques with in situ sampling for accurate, cost-effective monitoring of SOC stocks. Develop a comprehensive monitoring, reporting, and verification (MRV) framework to ensure accuracy and integrate multiple data sources (Andries et al., 2021).
- Utilize geostatistical techniques and GIS to analyze soil organic matter (SOM). Focus on areas with low SOM to guide sustainable soil management and regional planning in line with European Common Agricultural Policy objectives (Marchetti et al., 2012).
- Use machine-learning models that accurately predict centennially stable SOC fractions, crucial for improving soil health monitoring and carbon cycle models (Cécillon et al., 2021).

- Implement the Open Soil Index (OSI) as a practical framework for assessing soil health in agricultural fields, enabling tailored and sustainable farming practices to optimize crop production and ecosystem functions (Ros et al., 2022).
- Use AI-generated soil maps from the Soil Data Cube to better manage fields. These maps provide yearly, high-resolution estimates of SOC and clay content, improving soil management and sustainability, in Lithuania (Samarinas et al., 2023).

6. Facilitate Sustainability Transitions

6.1. Compliance with Policies, Schemes, and Strategies

- Advocate for an EU-wide, legally binding Soil Health Law that ensures standardized soil biodiversity protection, integrates incentive-based land management practices, and develops predictive models for soil biodiversity's spatial and temporal heterogeneity (Köninger et al., 2022).
- Implement soil conservation measures within the EU Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) to mitigate projected increases in soil erosion by 2050, emphasizing cover crops and minimal soil disturbance, particularly in high-erosion areas. Align these strategies with agro-environmental goals to protect soil health and sustainability across the EU and UK (Panagos et al., 2021).
- Adopt sustainable soil management practices per the European Green Deal, including reducing pesticide and fertilizer use, conserving wetlands, enhancing SOC, expanding organic farming, and promoting land restoration. Engage with the EU Soil Observatory to track progress towards climate neutrality and soil sustainability by 2050 (Montanarella & Panagos, 2021).
- Consider policy measures such as Biodiversity 2030, Farm to Fork, Chemicals Strategies, Circular Economy Action Plan, European Climate Law, Fit for 55 package, Zero Pollution Action Plan, and EU Soil Strategy for 2030 (Panagos et al., 2022).
- Tailor agri-environment schemes (AES) in the EU to individual farming contexts for effective climate change mitigation, soil health improvement, and enhanced ecosystem services (Stetter et al., 2022).
- Acknowledge the EU's 40-year investment in soil research and engage with initiatives like Horizon Europe's 'A Soil Deal for Europe' and the proposed Soil Monitoring Law to promote soil health and sustainability (Arias-Navarro et al., 2023).
- Encourage regenerative agriculture practices to improve environmental performance across diverse farming systems and emphasize the need for incentives to support this transition (Schreefel et al., 2022).
- Develop tailored soil management approaches based on soil-specific characteristics to enhance soil health and quality, contributing to sustainable development goals and EU Green Deal objectives (Bonfante et al., 2020).
- Implement an Organic Stewardship Scheme under Rural Development Regulation to facilitate the transition to organic farming, promote environmental benefits, and support sustainable agriculture in diversified rural economies (O'riordan & Cobb, 2001).

- Adopt legume cultivation to diversify crops and reduce environmental impacts, leveraging agroecological practices and staying adaptable to political and economic changes (Cusworth et al., 2021).
- Integrate agricultural policies that prevent or reduce soil erosion to maintain soil health and productivity (Lugato et al., 2016).
- Facilitate sustainable cultivation systems and management strategies (in Germany) to mitigate the negative impacts of bioenergy cropping on soil health, particularly in the face of climate change (Ruf et al., 2021).

6.2. Collaborative Learning and Knowledge Sharing Platforms, Programs, and Services

- Collaborate with local stakeholders and integrate their knowledge with experimental research towards sustainable agricultural development (Allan et al., 2013).
- Facilitate access to agroecological inputs and establish multi-stakeholder platforms to overcome economic constraints and knowledge gaps, enabling a transition from pesticide-heavy practices to agroecological methods in agriculture (Boulestreau et al., 2021).
- Promote collaborative farming networks and knowledge-sharing platforms to enhance collective capacity in soil management (Skaalsveen et al., 2020).
- Address the urgent need for sustainable soil management by engaging with the Horizon Europe Mission "A Soil Deal for Europe," utilizing living labs and lighthouses for local solutions, innovation, and education (Löbmann et al., 2022).
- Enhance soil knowledge access by tailoring content and improving sharing mechanisms. Promote scientific mediators and collaborative platforms like Living Labs and Lighthouse farms to foster local sustainable soil management in Europe (Mason et al., 2023).
- Foster joint learning among farmers, researchers, and stakeholders through "Living Labs" and system experiments to achieve UN SDGs and EU Green Deal objectives by 2030. Emphasize soil health, use tailored indicators for ecosystem services, and guide farm subsidies to promote sustainable land management (Bouma et al., 2022a).
- Shift from abstract sustainability discussions to concrete actions through collaborative learning initiatives like the European Commission's missions. Participate in "living labs" for soil health assessments and ecosystem service indicators to achieve SDGs and the EU Green Deal, fostering innovative environmental regulations in agriculture (Bouma, 2022a).
- Adopt soil security practices focusing on the 5C's: care, capability, capacity, capital, and condition. Engage stakeholders and use data to assess ecosystem services, guiding sustainable farming. Implement these strategies through "Living Labs" and "Lighthouses" to progress towards five key SDGs (Bouma, 2023a).
- Participate in soil health monitoring programs such as earthworm assessments to support sustainable soil management practices (Stroud, 2019).

- Collaborate with researchers and farmers globally to enhance soil ecosystem understanding through earthworm surveys supported by social media, with scientists providing online feedback. Emphasize the importance of earthworm monitoring for soil health and suggest improvements like photo verification and integrating soil properties for effective knowledge transfer (Stroud & Goulding, 2022).
- Engage with initiatives and projects that characterise the density and diversity of bacterial communities in soils to assess microbial biogeography and the impact of land use on soil biodiversity (Ranjard et al., 2010).
- Engage in projects like H3 (Healthy soil, Healthy food, Healthy people) to transform food systems. Focus on early interventions like biofortification and food reformulation to enhance nutrition and sustainability, collaborating with stakeholders for impactful outcomes (Jackson et al., 2021).
- Coordinate innovation design across system levels and stakeholders, supporting the agroecological transition of agrifood systems. Examples of designed innovations include organic mulching cropping systems, crop diversification with plot exchange, and transparent soil health management in field transactions (Boulestreau et al., 2023).
- Advocate for enhanced capacity building in Agricultural Advisory Services (AAS) to address constraints such as limited funding, inadequate adviser training, and motivational factors, thereby improving access to soil health management advice and supporting the transition to healthy soils (Ingram et al., 2022).
- Leverage the resources and expertise of the European Society for Soil Conservation (ESSC) to enhance soil science and promote sustainable soil management. ESSC offers research, knowledge exchange, and policy guidance to address soil degradation, protection, and conservation, emphasizing soil's role in environmental protection and agricultural productivity (Dazzi et al., 2019).

6.3. Overcoming the Barriers to Adoption of Conservation Practices

- Address technical, political, social, and economic drivers and barriers to dealing with soil challenges (Vanino et al., 2023).
- Recognize agroforestry's benefits for ecosystem services and resource optimization. Despite policy recognition, adoption is limited due to challenges. Support policy recommendations and an EU AF strategy for sustainable land use (Mosquera-Losada et al., 2023).
- Address barriers to crop rotation (in Ukraine) for climate resilience and soil health (Kopytko & Pruneddu, 2018).
- Adopt legume cultivation to diversify crops and reduce environmental impacts, leveraging agroecological practices and staying adaptable to political and economic changes (Cusworth et al., 2021).
- Facilitate Miscanthus adoption (in the UK) for sustainable bioenergy by addressing challenges like geography and transport costs through cultivar development and improved processing station distribution, contributing to efforts to achieve net-zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2050 (von Hellfeld et al., 2022).

- Increase stakeholder commitment and advocate for a European Soil Directive to improve soil health, as decision-makers are aware of soil issues, but public interest and national policies are lacking (Dumitraşcu et al., 2019).
- Recognize diverse stakeholders in sustainable soil management, including value chain participants and policymakers. Use the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) to prioritize criteria and understand interests and power dynamics, as shown in the EU mission "Soil Health and Food" (Kik et al., 2021).
- Encourage European farmers to prioritize soil multi-functionality beyond productivity. Address challenges like insufficient proof of soil degradation, limited awareness of soil function synergies, lack of ecosystem service remuneration, inadequate support, and lack of incentives and regulations on soil management (Schröder et al., 2020).
- Address cognitive lock-ins in farmers' decision-making to overcome barriers to adopting sustainable practices like crop diversification with legumes. Focus on context-specific socio-technical settings to promote transitions toward sustainable agri-food systems (Weituschat et al., 2022).
- Facilitate agroecological practices in conventional systems, such as Almeria's greenhouse sector, to strengthen farmers' connection to nature and promote sustainable agriculture transitions (Giagnocavo et al., 2022).
- Foster entrepreneurial identity in farmers to increase adoption of sustainable practices, as seen in initiatives like the Carta del Mulino. This approach is crucial for effectively addressing agricultural challenges (Rossi et al., 2023).
- Promote carbon farming in organic vegetable cultivation to boost soil health, and biodiversity, and reduce emissions through cover cropping and reduced tillage, while ensuring widespread adoption through farmer education, policy support, and research efforts (Avasiloaiei et al., 2023).
- Address gaps in sustainable soil management by prioritizing research on soil carbon stocks, soil degradation, and fertility. Develop models and monitoring programs, enhance research transfer to practitioners, strengthen knowledge brokers, and promote peer-to-peer communication and targeted advice to support sustainable practices in Europe (Thorsøe et al., 2023).
- Engage with voluntary certification schemes to address environmental, social, and economic sustainability issues and advocate for fair treatment within the (banana) production and trade system (Bebber, 2023).
- Evaluate soil characteristics at the European scale for quality, health, and ecosystem services, particularly under initiatives like the European Green Deal. Advocate for harmonization procedures and increased cooperation among countries and with the EU to effectively utilize soil data for developing sustainable soil management policies and indicators (Cornu et al., 2023).
- Adopt sustainable agricultural and land management practices, in Central and Southeast Europe, to combat soil degradation caused by diverse topography, deforestation, climate change, and unsustainable practices. Implement uniform soil quality assessment criteria to improve productivity and resilience against desertification (Günel et al., 2015).

- Embrace soil health initiatives to enhance agricultural productivity and mitigate climate change by focusing on increasing SOC levels. Promote the co-benefits of better soil management, including improved natural capital, climate change mitigation, and better crop and animal performance, with knowledge exchange and robust monitoring (McGuire et al., 2022).
- Adopt the soil security concept as a roadmap for sustainable development to balance ecosystem services, supporting the United Nations' SDGs and the European Union's Green Deal objectives (Bouma, 2020).

7. Encourage Sufficiency and Consider Cultural Values

- Address food losses and waste (FLW) in primary production per the EU Waste Framework Directive to boost farm sustainability. Focus on sectors like horticulture and tackle causes like pests and unharvestable produce to reduce FLW (O'Connor et al., 2022).
- Recognize soil fertility's historical significance for health, nutrition, and prosperity. Adapt past soil health strategies to current social, economic, and environmental changes to boost food productivity while maintaining soil nutrients (Güldner et al., 2021).
- Embrace biodynamic agriculture's spiritual aspects to foster a deeper connection with soil, recognizing the agency of soil biota and promoting reciprocal care (Pigott, 2021).
- Embrace soils' cultural and natural heritage value in policies. Incorporate soil profiles into heritage inventories and leverage programs like Horizon Europe and Natura 2000 to enhance soil literacy and interdisciplinary collaboration (Costantini, 2023).
- Consider diverse stakeholder perceptions of sustainability, from reducing meat consumption and food waste to promoting organic farming and self-sufficiency. Use these perspectives to encourage healthy diets, boost fruit and vegetable production, and build stakeholder trust for systemic changes (Röös et al., 2023).

Economic Dimension

8. Create Inclusive Value through Innovative Approaches

- Implement 4R nutrient stewardship for phosphorus (P) fertilizer to improve water quality, soil health, and biodiversity while maximizing productivity. Adapt to regional P surplus and collaborate with scientists and industry stakeholders for sustainable P management (Bruulsema et al., 2019).
- Develop and integrate soil-health-focused land management practices in living labs into long-term business plans to support sustainable agriculture aligned with UN SDGs and the EU Green Deal (Bouma et al., 2021).
- Promote upcoming food innovations like plant-based meat, personalized nutrition, regenerative and urban agriculture, and packaging innovations to enhance health, food security, and sustainability (Zickafoose et al., 2022).
- Prioritize soil health understanding, proactive monitoring, and engagement with government agencies to adopt sustainable land management practices addressing climate change, alongside considering efficiency, cost, regulations, and market demand (Feliciano, 2022).

9. Develop Diversified and Productive Solutions

9.1. Integrated Soil and Crop Management Practices

- Prioritize extensive cultivation practices in hazelnut, grapevine, and Citrus orchards to preserve soil functionality and quality (Biasi et al., 2021).
- Enhance Integrated Pest Management (IPM) practices to optimize soil health in orchards (Daelemans et al., 2022).
- Adopt organic production systems for almonds to enhance quality and offset yield reductions with higher market prices (Cárceles Rodríguez et al., 2023).
- Integrate hydopedology with soil physics and pedology for enhanced ecosystem services and soil security (Bouma, 2023b).
- Promote sustainable agriculture by integrating soil health management with UN SDGs and EU Green Deal objectives (Bouma et al., 2021).
- Adopt integrated soil management practices to improve soil health and ecosystem services (Williams et al., 2020).
- Utilize diverse plant communities (e.g., legume-based cover crops) to optimize soil fertility, weed suppression, and support beneficial invertebrates (Storkey et al., 2015).
- Integrate *Lupinus albus* as a winter crop with industrial hemp to enhance soil recovery during phytoextraction, promoting green manure and bacterial growth (Fumagalli et al., 2014).
- Implement diverse soil and crop management practices, including cover crops and animal manure, to maintain long-term soil quality and enhance earthworm density (De Notaris et al., 2021).
- Integrate legume/cereal cover crops in organic olive orchards to enhance parasitic wasp activity while minimizing non-target impacts (Volakakis et al., 2022).
- Implement Soil Improving Cropping Systems (SICS) with cover crops, mulching, and minimum tillage to mitigate soil erosion and increase SOC stocks (Bartman et al., 2022).
- Integrate landscape ecology approaches to predict the effects of land management on soil health and crop yield (Stockdale et al., 2019).
- Implement herbicide-free no-till systems, managing weeds with diverse crop rotations and cover cropping (Colbach & Cordeau, 2022).
- Harness hedgerows for biodiversity conservation, climate change mitigation, and soil health (Tilzey, 2021).
- Adopt strategic choices like land renting and crop rotations to mitigate the economic impacts of environmentally oriented production systems (Rossing et al., 1997).
- Promote perennial grains, such as intermediate wheatgrass, to enhance soil health, water quality, and food security in Western European farming systems (Duchene et al., 2019).
- Implement burial of crop residues and two-year wheat rotations to increase SOC and nitrogen content in Mediterranean rainfed conditions (Bonciarelli et al., 2016).
- Enhance soil quality in barley-maize cropping systems through diversified rotations and reduced tillage to improve soil structure (Manachini et al., 2009).

- Enhance water management, develop climate-resistant crops, and adopt climate-smart practices to address climate change impacts (Srivastav et al., 2021).
- Plan and diversify crop rotations to enhance financial stability and soil health in response to climate change predictions (Bane et al., 2021).
- Diversify agricultural systems with structural landscape elements, organic fertilization, and conservation tillage to address soil degradation (Strauss et al., 2023).
- Implement long-term farming strategies like crop rotation and tillage methods to enhance soil health and sustainability (Babin et al., 2019).
- Adopt diversified conservation practices like reduced tillage and cover cropping to enhance soil diversity in semi-arid Mediterranean agroecosystems (Sánchez-Moreno et al., 2018).
- Incorporate a broad approach to conservation agriculture, including cover cropping, crop rotations, and precision farming, to achieve environmental and economic benefits (Cooper et al., 2020).
- Integrate perennial wheat genotypes to leverage the benefits of taller plants and robust root systems for sustainability (Baronti et al., 2022).
- Incorporate overwinter cover crops in cereal production to increase spring barley yield and nitrogen concentration (Holland et al., 2021).
- Balance rainfed agriculture with building water reservoirs to boost agricultural profitability and stabilize populations (Esgalhado & Guimaraes, 2020).
- Adopt mixed farming systems combining organic farming and grazing to enhance soil quality and ecosystem services (Zani et al., 2021).
- Transition to extensive grazing systems in sheep meat production to reduce concentrate reliance and enhance sustainability (Bhatti et al., 2020).
- Integrate instrumented farm-scale trials to assess economic-environmental trade-offs in pasture-based ruminant systems (Takahashi et al., 2018).

9.2. Innovations and Technological Integration

- Integrate legumes into diverse products and farming systems to promote sustainable food systems in Europe (Ferreira et al., 2021).
- Promote conservation and organic agriculture for food legume production through technology transfer and participatory approaches (Siddique et al., 2012).
- Explore cover crop mixtures in Mediterranean vineyards to enhance grape production and quality while managing water stress (Raffa et al., 2022).
- Use wheat straw to remediate heavy metal contamination in soils and integrate circular economy principles (Golia, 2023).
- Utilize carbon capture-based organo-mineral fertilizers as an alternative to conventional mineral fertilizers (Burak & Sakrabani, 2023).
- Use LiDAR-based tools to minimize nutrient loss and erosion for better agricultural planning (Hayes et al., 2022).
- Develop agroecological farming practices with large herbivores to promote conservation, agriculture, and human activities (Balfour et al., 2021).
- Redesign farm systems to act as carbon sinks by integrating perennial crops and soil health awareness (Johansson et al., 2022).

- Optimize soil management in organic vineyards with treatments like alternate tillage and temporary cover crops to improve yield and grape quality (Gatti et al., 2022).
- Adopt affordable agricultural technologies to improve soil health and crop production, addressing food safety and nutrition education (Hatzenbuehler & Peña-Lévano, 2022).

5. Annex 2. Factors influencing SHP adoption by arable farmers in the Netherlands

Factors	Drivers	Barriers
Knowledge/Social Networking	Farmer colleagues, Education, First-hand experience, Study groups, Advisors, Sectoral meetings and fairs, etc.	-
Institutional	Certification, Partner pressure, Policy/CAP subsidies	Policy inconsistencies, Complex subsidy systems, etc.
Technical	Agronomic, Economic, Innovation Characteristics	High investment costs, Agronomic challenges, Climate issues
Personal	Tenure	Age, Tenure, Heritage

❖ Knowledge/Social Networking factors

The adoption of Soil Health Practices (SHPs) among arable farmers is significantly influenced by the creation and dissemination of knowledge. Farmers derive their understanding of SHPs, including benefits, risks, and implementation strategies, through extensive social networks. These networks encompass local farmer groups, business interactions with sectoral companies (e.g., buyers), and connections with knowledge institutes and universities. Such networks facilitate the exchange of valuable information crucial for informed decision-making regarding SHPs.

❖ Institutional factors

Institutional pressures play a crucial role in the adoption of SHPs, driven by certification requirements, business partner expectations, and government policies. These factors create a framework within which farmers operate, influencing their decision-making processes.

❖ Technical factors

The implementation of SHPs involves various technical considerations, including agronomic, financial, and innovation-related factors. These aspects directly affect the feasibility and attractiveness of SHPs for farmers.

❖ Personal Factors

Personal factors, such as the age of the farmer and the presence of a successor, also influence the adoption of SHPs. These factors reflect individual motivations and the perceived long-term benefits of changing current practices.

6. References

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